

Economics of African biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics for prosperity

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Abstract

African biodiversity is at a transformative juncture where advances in genome sequencing and bioinformatics could support productivity gains, structural transformation, and greater economic resilience. In this work, we examine how the generation, sharing, and use of Digital Sequence Information (DSI) shape the economic returns from biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics in African economies. Using a tripartite analytical lens spanning biodiversity, genomics, and economics, we combine macroeconomic simulations with qualitative evidence on institutional and policy conditions, drawing on emerging continent-wide coordination efforts catalysed through the African BioGenome Project (AfricaBP). Our results demonstrate that expanding sequencing and bioinformatics capacities and innovations can increase aggregate output and capital income across African regions, with gains up to 26% in the Economic Community of West African States and the East African Community. Labor income declines by around 18% in the Arab Maghreb Union due to the strong substitution between labor and capital, and consequently an increase in capital intensity in the most productive sectors. Productivity gains propagate through structural transmission channels and sectoral linkages, yet returns remain uneven across countries, with benefit-cost ratios exceeding 22 in Nigeria and falling below 1 unity in smaller economies, demonstrating that for every US\$1 Nigeria invests in sequencing biodiversity genomes it will receive US\$22 in return. We show that translating genomic innovation into broad-based prosperity requires simple and implementable national Access and Benefit Sharing frameworks, supported by bespoke Intellectual Property rules, and clear attribution and recognition practices. Increased DSI generation and use could also create fiscal space to support implementation of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF), while strengthening research independence and local scientific capabilities. The data presented in this work provides the first foundational quantitative assessment on how African countries could self-finance their commitments in the KMGBF through DSI.

Main

The economy and biodiversity, at both microeconomic and macroeconomic levels (Gardes-Landolfini et al., 2024; Nakata, 2025; Rawat et al., 2024), are closely interconnected (Felardo, 2016; Reyes-García et al., 2025) through what is commonly described as Natural Capital (OECD, 2021). As a core component of Natural Capital, biodiversity encompasses the variety of terrestrial and aquatic life, including diversity within and between species and ecosystems (UNEP Convention on Biological Diversity, 2011a). The broader economy includes all production, distribution, and consumption of goods and services, while its interaction with biodiversity is most

evident through renewable biological resources such as crops, forests, fisheries, and livestock used for products, materials, energy, and industrial inputs (Khanna et al., 2024; Riemann et al., 2025; Wiold, 2013). At the macroeconomic scale, policy seeks to attain the maximum sustainable real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Lawn, 2008; Soto et al., 2025) (see also Table 1), whereas at the microeconomic scale biodiversity conservation is addressed through market-based mechanisms that value ecosystem services and incentivise local stewardship (Harzer & Quaas, 2026; Martin, 2020).

Africa is one of the most biodiversity-dependent economic regions globally, hosting a substantial share of the world's biodiversity and several recognised biodiversity hotspots (Mindje Kayumba et al., 2025; Myers et al., 2000; Neugarten et al., 2024; Smith & Matimele, 2025). Many of these hotspots are shrinking under increasing anthropogenic pressures (Clements et al., 2025). Biodiversity underpins human well-being (Meng et al., 2024), providing food and income (Naeem et al., 2016), including agricultural systems such as cocoa cultivation in Côte d'Ivoire (Wang & Pfister, 2024), as well as construction materials, industrial raw materials, medicines, and ecosystem stability (Lovelock et al., 2025). It also forms the biological basis for improvements in plants, animals, and microbial life (IPBES, 2019; Liang et al., 2015; Wagg et al., 2019).

Economic dependence on biodiversity is increasingly quantifiable. In 2023, over half of global GDP, approximately US\$50 trillion, was generated by economic activities that are moderately to highly dependent on nature (Evison et al., 2023). Natural Capital is being degraded at an unprecedented pace due to adverse human activities (Díaz et al., 2019; Jaureguiberry et al., 2022; Keck et al., 2025; Yang et al., 2025), posing systemic economic risks. These risks are particularly acute in Sub-Saharan Africa, where approximately 24% of pre-colonial and pre-industrial fauna and flora abundance have disappeared, ranging from less than 20% loss in disturbance-adapted herbaceous species to around 80% loss of large mammals (Clements et al., 2025). Natural capital supports about 70% of Sub-Saharan African communities (African Natural Capital Alliance, 2023), sustains livelihoods for 62% of the rural population (IPBES, 2018), and contributes approximately 62% of African GDP (African Natural Capital Alliance, 2023). This dependence translates into high exposure to nature-based risks, including potential GDP contractions of up to 9.7% annually by 2030 due to ecosystems' services collapse (Johnson et al., 2021), with consequences extending beyond Africa (Fabre & Vertier, 2024).

Africa's biodiversity depends on genetics, species, ecosystems, and landscape diversity to sustain ecosystem health and biosphere stability (Bilande et al., 2025). Genetic diversity underpins all other biodiversity levels (O'Brien et al., 2025), supports evolutionary adaptation (Fady & Scotti-Saintagne, 2025), and its loss can cascade across species, ecosystems, and landscapes (Mualim et al., 2025). These patterns of biodiversity and associated conservation strategies, well documented at

landscape and ecosystem scales, provide the foundation for effective management and integration into landscape planning and ecosystem service frameworks (Darvishi et al., 2024; Estrada-Carmona et al., 2022; Kleijn et al., 2020; Kremen & Merenlender, 2018; Meier et al., 2025; Priyadarshana et al., 2024; Ye et al., 2025).

Parallel to its ecological systems, Africa has a changing economic and governance landscape, shaped by African Regional Economic Communities (REC) (Killander, 2018), the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) (Chukwuemeka et al., 2022; Debrah et al., 2024; Kwasi Tiekou & Yakohene, 2023; Preku & Anyigba, 2025; United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, 2025), and special economic zones (Rodríguez-Pose et al., 2022). Beyond facilitating economic integration, these frameworks (i.e. RECs and AfCFTA) influence resource allocation, research coordination, and investments in scientific and biodiversity infrastructure. Yet, only 8.4% of 368,516 international co-publications from African organisations involve co-publications between at least two African countries, revealing substantial unrealised potential for continental and regional research collaborations (Dosso et al., 2023).

Economic policies and structural factors further shape biodiversity outcomes requiring the enactment and implementation of strong policies and institutions to better manage, protect and sustainably use African biodiversity (Amare et al., 2024). This is evidenced in 32 Sub-Saharan African countries (1996–2020), where population growth, natural resources' dependence, and foreign direct investment are correlated with biodiversity loss, whereas higher incomes and trade openness supported growth and, within certain limits, biodiversity conservation through technological upgrades and institutional reforms (Adangbedou & Lokonon, 2025). Likewise, agricultural strategies traditionally emphasising improved crop varieties can, when guided by policy, simultaneously advance food production and conservation, as shown by recent studies on Ethiopian durum wheat integrating microeconomic, macroeconomic, and agronomic data (Gotor et al., 2025).

Several initiatives have emerged to catalogue biodiversity at genetic and genomic scales, including the African BioGenome Project (AfricaBP, <https://africanbiogenome.org>) (Ebenezer et al., 2022), the 1000 South African Biodiversity Genomes Project (Meyer et al., 2025), the Vertebrate Genomes Project (Rhie et al., 2021), the Sanger Tree of Life (Threlfall & Blaxter, 2021), and the 1000 Plant Genomes Project (10KP) (Cheng et al., 2018). While the scientific and conservation rationale for sequencing biodiversity genomes are well established (Blaxter et al., 2022; Theissinger et al., 2023), limited attention has been given to the economic case for biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics, particularly in Africa. Economic impacts have been examined in human genomics (House et al., 2025; Howley et al., 2025) and non-genomic biodiversity domains, including the Human Genome Project (Tripp & Gruebe, 2021), biodiversity valuation (Dasgupta, 2021; Helm & Hepburn, 2012), microbiobiodiversity (Han et al., 2023; Mostafa et al., 2024),

wildlife (Bojo, 1996), and One Health approaches (Auplish et al., 2024; Mamabolo et al., 2025). However, none provide a comprehensive quantitative assessment of the biodiversity, genomics, bioinformatics, and economics nexus.

Within this context, the Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (AI) subcommittee of the AfricaBP seeks to leverage biodiversity genomics, bioinformatics, data science, and AI to generate actionable impacts across Africa. A previous Cost-Benefit Analysis of biodiversity sequencing focused narrowly on Morocco and emphasised the bioeconomy without integrating microeconomic and macroeconomic dynamics (Hayah et al., 2025), nor did it link predicted benefits to national economies or interactions between microeconomic and macroeconomic systems.

Here, we: (1) provide current understanding of African biodiversity hotspots and their significance for ecosystems and economies; (2) identify the contributions of biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics to African biodiversity and economic systems; (3) map intellectual property generation to genomic capacities and access and benefit-sharing; (4) evaluate microeconomic and macroeconomic cost-benefit dynamics of genomic integration; (5) propose strategies to maximise economic impacts; and (6) kickstart the establishment of an African biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics for social impact initiative.

Table 1: Glossary of technical terms and their abbreviations

S/N	Term	Definition	Reference
1	Business-as-usual scenario (BAU)	The counterfactual or the situation against which we compare the impact of the changes of TFP, of capital share and of the elasticity of substitution that we introduce in the simulated scenarios.	(Robichaud et al., 2013)
2	Capital Share Parameter ($\beta_{k,j,z}^{KD}$)	The weight of capital of type k in the CES composite capital function for industry j in region z . It determines the relative efficiency of capital of type k in the total composite capital.	
3	Composite Capital Demand ($KDC_{j,z,t}$)	Demand for composite capital by industry j in region z in period t . It is a CES aggregate of different types of capital (e.g., reproducible capital, land, natural resources) used in the production process. KDC enters in the value-added function and appears in equations related to production, factor demand, and price aggregation.	
4	Composite Capital Rental Rate ($RC_{j,z,t}$)	Rental rate of composite capital for industry j in region z at time t . It is the price per unit of the composite capital aggregate $KDC_{j,z,t}$ used in production, calculated as a weighted average of the tax-inclusive rental rates of all capital types.	
5	Composite Labor Demand ($LDC_{j,z,t}$)	Demand for composite labour by industry j in region z in period t . The composite labor is a CES aggregate of different labour types (e.g., skilled and unskilled labour) used in production.	
6	Composite Labor Wage Rate ($WC_{j,z,t}$)	Wage rate in industry j of composite labour in region z in period t . Weighted average of tax-inclusive wage rates of all labour types.	
7	Computable General Equilibrium Model (CGEM)	A class of economic models based on microeconomic foundations and general equilibrium theory, that represent the economy as a system of simultaneous equations describing the behavior of producers, households, governments, and the rest of the world, and that are solved numerically using actual economic data to analyze the economy-wide impacts of policy changes or external shocks (Dixon & Jorgenson, 2013; Shoven & Whalley, 1992).	
8	Constant Elasticity of Substitution (CES) Function	The CES function is a production or utility function in which the elasticity of substitution between inputs or goods remains constant. It allows modeling the ability to substitute one factor (or good) for another while maintaining the same level of output (or utility).	

S/N	Term	Definition	Reference
		$Q = A \left[\sum_i \alpha_i X_i^\rho \right]^{\frac{1}{\rho}}$ where $\sigma = \frac{1}{1-\rho}$ is the constant elasticity of substitution. $\beta_{j,z}^{D,x1}$: Share parameter (CET – total productions – domestic sales). $\beta_{j,z}^{EX,x1}$: Share parameter (CET – total productions – exports). $\beta_{k,j,z}^{KD}$: Share parameter (CES – composite capital). $\beta_{l,j,z}^{LD}$: Share parameter (CES – composite labor). $\beta_{i,z}^{M1}$: Share parameter (CES – imports – domestic internal demand). $\beta_{i,zj}^{M2}$: Share parameter (CES – composite imports). $\beta_{j,z}^{VA}$: Share parameter (CES – value added). $\beta_{j,z,zj}^{X2}$: Share parameter (CET – composite exports).	
9	Disposable Household Income ($YDH_{z,t}$)	The total income available to households in region z during period t after payment of direct (income) taxes. It represents the amount households can either consume or save. It is calculated as total household income minus household income taxes.	
10	Total Production ($XS_{j,z,t}$)	The total output of industry j in region z during period t , representing the total volume produced by this industry. This output is allocated among the different market outlets: exports, domestic market supply, and, where applicable, the provision of international transport margin services.	
11	Household Capital Income ($YHK_{z,t}$)	Gross income received by households in region z during period t from the use of capital in production, calculated as the sum of all rental payments made by industries for all types of capital (reproducible capital, land, natural resources), before deduction of direct taxes and including depreciation (capital consumption allowance).	
12	Household Consumption ($C_{i,z,t}$)	Consumption of commodity i by households in region z in period t . Determined by the Linear Expenditure System (LES) derived using a Stone-Geary utility function.	
13	Household Labor Income ($YHL_{z,t}$)	Total gross income received by households in region z in period t as labor earnings. It is the sum of wages paid to all labor types across all industries in the region.	

S/N	Term	Definition	Reference
14	Household Total Income ($YH_{z,t}$)	Total household income in region z in period t . It is the sum of labour and capital income.	
15	Input Shares	Parameters or ratios that represent the proportion of a given input (e.g., a commodity, labor type, or capital type) in the total cost or total quantity of an aggregate input used by an industry or demanded by final users.	
16	Intermediate Consumption ($CI_{z,j,t}$)	Total consumption of intermediate inputs by industry j in region z during period t . A fixed-proportion between all intermediate inputs used in production: the aggregated inputs are considered strictly complementary, with no possibility of substitution, following a Leontief production function.	
17	Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP)	The Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) database (specifically GTAP.11) provides the global social accounting matrix (SAM) used as the primary data source for calibrating the CGE model. It contains detailed, consistent bilateral trade, production, consumption, tax, and factor-income data for multiple regions and sectors.	
18	Government Income ($YG_{z,t}$)	Total government income in region z in period t . It includes tax revenues collected from households and taxes on production, products, and imports.	
19	Gross Domestic Product ($GDP_{z,t}^{MP}$)	Gross domestic product at market prices in region z during period t , equal to payments to factors, plus production taxes other than labor or capital taxes already included in factor costs, plus taxes on products and imports.	
20	Income-based (Y) variables	A set of variables that measure the flow of earnings, tax revenues, and factor payments accruing to households, governments, and the rest of the world within each region during a given period. They are derived from the income side of the circular flow and are used to compute disposable income, savings, and macroeconomic balances.	
21	Price Index of Intermediate Consumption ($PCI_{j,z,t}$)	It is the average cost in industry j in region z at time t per unit of the baskets of intermediate inputs used by that industry, calculated as a weighted average of the purchaser prices of all intermediate commodities with respect to a base year.	
22	Rest-of-the-World total Income ($YROW_{z,t}$)	Payments received by the rest of the world from region z for imports (including international transport margins).	

S/N	Term	Definition	Reference
23	Real Economic Variables/QP variables	QP variables (also called non-Y variables) are a set of model variables that represent physical or volume quantities in the economy, each paired with a corresponding price index. They are used to compute monetary values by multiplying quantity by price, and they are separate from income (Y) variables, which are reported directly in value terms without a quantity-price split.	
24	Total Factor Productivity (TFP)	Total factor productivity (denoted $A_{z,t}^{VA}$) is a region-wide efficiency parameter used in the value-added production function. Its growth rate captures the portion of output growth not explained by growth of factor inputs (labour and capital), representing technological progress (Romer, 1990), organizational efficiency (Barro, 1990), resource quality (Lucas, 1988), and other non-input determinants of production efficiency (Mishkin, 2014).	
25	Trade flows	The bilateral movements of goods and services between regions. They are exports from one region to another and imports received in return. In the PEP-w-t model, trade flows are valued at world prices and include associated international transport and trade margin services. They link domestic production and demand to the rest of the world and determine each region's external balance (current account).	
26	Unit Cost ($PP_{j,z,t}$)	Unit cost of industry j in region z and time t including taxes directly related to the use of capital and labour but excluding other taxes on production. Weighted sum of value-added price and intermediate consumption price.	
27	Value Added ($VA_{j,z,t}$)	Value added of industry j in region z in period t . It is modelled as a CES combination of composite labour and composite capital, scaled by multifactor productivity.	

Current landscape of African biodiversity hotspots

Africa's nine biodiversity hotspots form part of a global network of 36 hotspots identified through a conservation prioritisation framework that concentrates endemism within areas experiencing acute habitat loss (Habel et al., 2019; Marchese, 2015; Myers et al., 2000; Smith & Matimele, 2025). While only about 18 percent of the world's highest-priority conservation land is formally protected (Neugarten et al., 2024), the framework's enduring significance lies in its capacity to translate spatial biodiversity patterns into a coherent rationale for global conservation investment (Smith & Matimele, 2025). Within this context, Africa's hotspots constitute indispensable elements of global natural capital, sustaining biodiversity and providing Nature's contributions to people, including carbon storage, water quality regulation, and crop pollination that sustains food security (Neugarten et al., 2024).

Looking ahead, these regions are projected to be among the most extensively transformed yet species rich and threatened landscapes by 2050 (Habel et al., 2019). The drivers of biodiversity loss vary across Africa's hotspots, with agro-economic pressures associated with population growth, rising incomes, and increasing food demand emerging as the dominant force (Habel et al., 2019).

At finer spatial scales, these global priorities translate into markedly different ecological risks and socio-economic pressures. In southern Africa, the Cape Floristic Region, Succulent Karoo, and Maputaland Pondoland Albany hotspots face interconnected and often unrecognised pressures (Lichtenberg et al., 2025). Predictive modelling suggests that 24.1% of unassessed plant species may already be threatened (Kandolo et al., 2024). In southern Afrotropical forest birds within the Maputaland Pondoland Albany hotspot, disrupted gene flow reveals a latent extinction risk linked to progressive landscape degradation (Mulaney et al., 2021).

Comparable climate-driven constraints are evident in the Eastern Afrotropical, where Ethiopia's Bale Mountains support high plant and faunal endemism yet face rising temperature pressures on narrowly endemic taxa with limited dispersal capacity (Fashing et al., 2022; Kidane et al., 2019; Mittermeier et al., 2004). This Eastern Afrotropical region extends into Kenya, overlapping with the Coastal Forests of Eastern Africa and the Horn of Africa hotspots (Marchese, 2015). The convergence of these systems has created a complex mosaic shaped by deep-time climatic and geological processes, delineating five distinct phytogeographical regions, including the Volcanic and Coastal Regions which preserve ancient endemic plant lineages (Zhang et al., 2022).

To the north, the Mediterranean Basin hotspot suffers from protection gaps, with nearly 80% of priority freshwater sites in North Africa remaining outside formal protected areas (Slimani et al., 2022). In West Africa, Cameroon spans major biogeographic boundaries, encompassing portions of the Guinean Forests and the Congo Basin hotspots (Beekmann et al., 2024; Oates et al., 2004). In Southwest

Cameroon, protected areas provide refuge, yet flagship species, including the Nigeria-Cameroon chimpanzee and forest elephant, continue to decline due to poaching rather than active management (Kupsch & Bobo, 2024).

Finally, the Madagascar and Indian Ocean Islands hotspot illustrates the tension between exceptional biodiversity and human dependence (Ralimanana et al., 2022). Despite a protected area network covering 10.4 percent of the land, nearly 90 percent of plant species are threatened, including 559 species with no formal protection (Ralimanana et al., 2022). Effective conservation in these hotspots requires addressing the socioeconomic drivers of biodiversity loss while exploring new opportunities for investment to safeguard Africa's unique biodiversity and enhance the benefits it provides to people and ecosystems.

Figure 1: Africa’s biodiversity hotspot is a shrinking treasure trove that must be conserved and sustainably managed. The figure shows biodiversity hotspots on and around the African continent. It further delineates all regions where biodiversity hotspots are located and is funded by organisations such as Critical Ecosystem Partnership Fund (CEPF). Terrestrial biodiversity hotspots are shown as green, and marine biodiversity is shown as lighter blue. Hotspots generally refer to regions where there are a minimum of 1500 vascular plants endemic to the region but have also lost 70% of native vegetation. Country localities are represented through points. The map data for this figure was provided courtesy of ArcWorldSupplement and the biodiversity information was generated by (Hoffman et al., 2016).

African Continental Free Trade Area and Regional Economic Areas powering African economic activities

Africa's recent push toward economic transformation is guided by frameworks such as the African Continental Free Trade Area (African Union, 2018). Launched in 2021, the AfCFTA aims to establish a single African market by harmonising diverse regional trade systems (Arreyndip, 2021). It covers a population of about 1.4 billion people and an estimated US \$3.4 trillion in combined GDP, and seeks to eliminate tariffs on approximately 90% of goods (Arreyndip, 2021).

Beyond trade liberalisation, the AfCFTA frames integration as a tool for inclusive development by advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), promoting gender equality, and strengthening food security (African Union, 2018). Its linkages to African Union (AU) Agenda 2063 (African Union, 2015) position it as a mechanism that supports technological upgrading and science-led innovation across the continent (Aniche, 2023). AfCFTA uses the (RECs) (Table 2) as building blocks and recognises their significance and achievements in facilitating intra-African trade, economic cooperation, and regional stability (African Union, 2018). Across the AfCFTA landscape, RECs are emerging as key drivers of biodiversity-based trade, harmonizing standards and strengthening natural-product value chains that connect conservation with inclusive economic growth (UNCTAD, 2021). Biological resources support economic resilience of key sectors in RECs, including agriculture, livestock, wildlife, and tourism (Ngongolo & Kyando, 2025). BioTrade initiatives illustrate how AU Agenda 2063's focus on science, technology, and innovation (STI) can intersect with trade integration by promoting the sustainable commercialization of biodiversity products across RECs, yet biodiversity and its genetic diversity remain largely absent from STI priority areas (see Table 2), and while the STISA-2024 strategy and AU Agenda 2063 identified biotechnology and genome editing as tools to enhance the sustainable use of biological diversity, boost food security, and drive industrial development, AfCFTA is currently limited in detailed environmental safeguards or mandatory biodiversity provisions (Benson & Judd, 2021; UNCTAD, 2021).

The magnitude of the economic effect of biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics depends on how regional economies absorb the new technologies, use available data, and benefit from the available knowledge to create innovant agricultural products (UNCTAD, 2021). Some RECs are more integrated than others in their overall market arrangements: for instance, East African Community (EAC) and Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) have achieved deep market integration (common markets with free movement of people and goods), while Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA) and Southern African Development Community (SADC) maintain large free trade zones (Gammadigbe, 2021). AfCFTA expands on Africa's regional economic communities but seeks a more unified continental market. It builds on REC achievements, from tariff reductions to transport corridors and monetary cooperation (Ajewumi et al., 2024), and aims to harmonise rules through a single rule of origin (The African

Continental Free Trade Area Secretariat, 2022). REC initiatives such as ECOWAS's agriculture strategy (Nwozor & Olanrewaju, 2020) and COMESA's currency arrangements (Davis, 2025) provide practical models for scaling up. At the same time, overlapping REC memberships create conflicting tariffs and transit rules, and coordination between RECs and the AfCFTA Secretariat remains limited (Byiers et al., 2024). Therefore, achieving smooth continental integration will require clearer alignment and carefully phased transitions across regions (Ajewumi et al., 2024).

Table 2: African regional economic areas (RECs) and member countries*

S/N	Regional Economic Community (REC)	Year of establishment of REC	Member countries	Some key focus areas (or areas of cooperation) for Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) in protocols, policies, or treaties	Number of researchers per million inhabitants (FTE*) (UNESCO Year 2023) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Combined GDP in USD (US\$) in 2023	Gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percent of GDP (UNESCO Year 2023**) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Relevant references
1	Southern African Development Community (SADC)	1992	Angola Botswana Comoros Democratic Republic of Congo Eswatini Lesotho Madagascar Malawi Mauritius Mozambique Namibia Seychelles South Africa Tanzania Zambia Zimbabwe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments in human capital development • Attracting and retaining scientific human capacity in the region • Gender equality and access to STI education • Forging strong relationships with the African Diaspora • Mobilising skills and expertise in the African Diaspora • Science, Technology, and Innovation Strategy for Africa (STISA) 	852.68 Note: This data is for Mauritius only. Data is not available for other SADC member states	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • \$769.77bn • \$847bn 2023 (GDP at Current Prices) 	0.23 Note: This data is for Mauritius only. Data is not yet available for other SADC member states	(Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf), 2022; Mo Ibrahim Foundation, 2025h; SADC, 2025; Southern African Development Community, 2008, 2025; Southern African Development Community (SADC) Secretariat, 2020)
2	Arab Maghreb Union (AMU)	1989	Algeria Libya Mauritania Morocco	Maghreb member states have not yet adopted or established a common STI protocol or policy	1782.46 Note: This data	\$490.48bn	Not Available	(Arab Maghreb Union, 2025; Djeflat, 2022;

S/N	Regional Economic Community (REC)	Year of establishment of REC	Member countries	Some key focus areas (or areas of cooperation) for Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) in protocols, policies, or treaties	Number of researchers per million inhabitants (FTE*) (UNESCO Year 2023) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Combined GDP in USD (US\$) in 2023	Gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percent of GDP (UNESCO Year 2023**) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Relevant references
			Tunisia		is for Algeria only. Data is not available for other AMU member states			Dosso et al., 2023; Mo Ibrahim Foundation, 2025a)
3	Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS)	1975	Benin Ivory Coast Gambia Ghana Guinea Guinea-Bissau Liberia Nigeria Senegal Sierra Leone Togo Cabo Verde	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthen national scientific and technological capabilities Proper application of science and technology Reduce dependence on foreign technology and promote individual and collective technology self-reliance Strengthen existing institutions and promote joint scientific research <p>Note: The ECOWAS Policy on Science, Technology and</p>	41.39 Note: This data is for Togo only. Data is not available for other ECOWAS member states	\$674.53bn	Not Available	(ECOWAS, 2025; ECOWAS Commission, 2010, 2012; Mègnigbèto, 2022; Mo Ibrahim Foundation, 2025f)

S/N	Regional Economic Community (REC)	Year of establishment of REC	Member countries	Some key focus areas (or areas of cooperation) for Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) in protocols, policies, or treaties	Number of researchers per million inhabitants (FTE*) (UNESCO Year 2023) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Combined GDP in USD (US\$) in 2023	Gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percent of GDP (UNESCO Year 2023**) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Relevant references
				Innovation is adopted through a Supplementary Act and Article 27 of the ECOWAS Treaty.				
4	East African Community (EAC)	re-established in 2000	Democratic Republic of Congo Burundi Kenya Rwanda Somalia South Sudan Uganda Tanzania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify, promote and grow special talents in STI Promote the use and development of indigenous knowledge and technology Disseminate and internalise new and emerging technologies Promote regional research centers of excellence Enhance collaboration in scientific and technological training of personnel 	115.47 Note: This is an average value (arithmetic mean) for Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda only. Data is not available for other EAC member states	\$330.67bn	0.63 Note: This is an average value (arithmetic mean) for Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda only. Data is not yet available for other EAC member states	(EAC, 2025; East African Community, 2007; Mo Ibrahim Foundation, 2025d; Ogada et al., 2022; Schneegans & Soete, 2024)
5	Economic Community of Central African	1983	Angola Burundi Cameroon Central African	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proper application of science and technology to agriculture, health, energy, hygiene, and conservation of the environment 	133.12 Note: This data	\$280.05bn	0.79 Note: This data	(Diamoneka, 2023; Economic Community of Central African States

S/N	Regional Economic Community (REC)	Year of establishment of REC	Member countries	Some key focus areas (or areas of cooperation) for Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) in protocols, policies, or treaties	Number of researchers per million inhabitants (FTE*) (UNESCO Year 2023) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Combined GDP in USD (US\$) in 2023	Gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percent of GDP (UNESCO Year 2023**) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Relevant references
	States (ECCAS)		Republic Chad Democratic Republic of Congo Republic of Congo Equatorial Guinea Gabon Rwanda São Tomé and Príncipe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote individual and collective technology reliance by seeking a favorable socio-economic balance between foreign and local technology contributions Harmonise and coordinate research, scientific services, and national technology development plans Promote exchange of researchers between member states 	is for Rwanda only. Data is not available for other ECCAS member states		is for Rwanda only. Data is not available for other ECCAS member states	(ECCAS), 1983; Mo Ibrahim Foundation, 2025e; Savadogo, 2018)
6	Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA)	1994	Burundi Comoros Democratic Republic of Congo Djibouti Egypt Eritrea Eswatini Ethiopia Kenya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build basic scientific and technological research capabilities as well as expertise in conventional low and indigenous technologies Development of applied sciences in related to agriculture, health, energy, soil science, oceans, 	408.88 Note: This is an average value (arithmetic mean) for Egypt, Kenya, Mauritius, Rwanda, and	\$1.13tn	0.63 Note: This is an average value (arithmetic mean) for Egypt, Kenya, Mauritius, Rwanda, and	(COMESA, 2025; Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA), 1993; Mo Ibrahim Foundation, 2025b)

S/N	Regional Economic Community (REC)	Year of establishment of REC	Member countries	Some key focus areas (or areas of cooperation) for Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) in protocols, policies, or treaties	Number of researchers per million inhabitants (FTE*) (UNESCO Year 2023) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Combined GDP in USD (US\$) in 2023	Gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percent of GDP (UNESCO Year 2023**) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Relevant references
			Libya Madagascar Malawi Mauritius Uganda Rwanda Seychelles Somalia Sudan Tunisia Zambia Zimbabwe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> minerals and the environment Enhance exchange programmes the training of personnel on conventional technologies and science-based high technologies as the quickest way to produce wealth Linking research and development to production units for integration with national development planning Local and international resource mobilisation Develop patent laws and establish national centres for commercialisation and innovation 	Uganda only. Data is not available for other COMESA member states		Uganda only. Data is not available for other COMESA member states	
7	Intergovernmental Authority on Development	1996	Djibouti Ethiopia Eritrea Kenya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote equitable access to quality and relevant education and skills 	213.29 Note: This is an	\$445.52bn	0.56	(Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD), 2020a, 2020b,

S/N	Regional Economic Community (REC)	Year of establishment of REC	Member countries	Some key focus areas (or areas of cooperation) for Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) in protocols, policies, or treaties	Number of researchers per million inhabitants (FTE*) (UNESCO Year 2023) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Combined GDP in USD (US\$) in 2023	Gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percent of GDP (UNESCO Year 2023**) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Relevant references
	(IGAD)		Somalia South Sudan Sudan Uganda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sustainable management and use of transboundary ecosystems ● Complements efforts of member states towards achieving food and nutrition security ● Increase investments in scientific research and discovery ● Promote indigenous knowledge and practices ● Establish an IGAD Regional Intellectual Property Rights Agency (RIPRA) to protect local institutions ● Strengthen regional and international cooperation in STI ● Enable knowledge transfer and exchange programmes <p>Note: IGAD implements its STI</p>	average value (arithmetic mean) for Kenya and Uganda only. Data is not available for other IGAD member states		Note: This is an average value (arithmetic mean) for Kenya and Uganda only. Data is not available for other IGAD member states	2023, 2025; Mo Ibrahim Foundation, 2025g)

S/N	Regional Economic Community (REC)	Year of establishment of REC	Member countries	Some key focus areas (or areas of cooperation) for Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) in protocols, policies, or treaties	Number of researchers per million inhabitants (FTE*) (UNESCO Year 2023) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Combined GDP in USD (US\$) in 2023	Gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percent of GDP (UNESCO Year 2023**) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Relevant references
				through documents such as the IGAD Regional Education Policy Framework and IGAD Regional Strategy 2021-2025				
8	Community of Sahel-Saharan States (CEN-SAD)	1998	Burkina Faso Eritrea Libya Comoros Gambia Egypt Ivory Coast Djibouti Guinea Guinea Bissau Sierra Leone Benin Central African Republic Ghana Mali Niger Senegal Sudan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combating drought, desertification and climate change Preservation of natural resources through research in the field of renewable energy Infrastructure development Economic, commercial, scientific and socio-cultural cooperation Harmonisation of scientific, technical and cultural systems in training courses 	292.36 Note: This is an average value (arithmetic mean) for Mali, Egypt, and Togo only. Data is not available for other CEN-SAD member states	\$1.46tn	0.61 Note: This is an average value (arithmetic mean) for Mali and Egypt only. Data is not available for other CEN-SAD member states	(CEN-SAD, 2025; Community of Sahel-Saharan States (CEN-SAD), 2013; Meze & Ezeanyej, 2025; Mo Ibrahim Foundation, 2025c)

S/N	Regional Economic Community (REC)	Year of establishment of REC	Member countries	Some key focus areas (or areas of cooperation) for Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) in protocols, policies, or treaties	Number of researchers per million inhabitants (FTE*) (UNESCO Year 2023) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Combined GDP in USD (US\$) in 2023	Gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percent of GDP (UNESCO Year 2023**) (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)	Relevant references
			Chad Somalia Nigeria Mauritania Togo Tunisia Morocco					

*Researchers in full-time equivalent (FTE) per million inhabitants

**For 2022 - 2021 data see also data for UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2025)

Economic modelling and analysis of African biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics

This study evaluates the economic impact of deploying genome sequencing technologies across African biodiversity using the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) Computable General Equilibrium Model (CGEM), specifically the PEP-w-t model (Robichaud et al., 2013). For this application, the model has been recalibrated using version 11 of the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) database (Hertel, 1997). The analysis covers regional blocs including the Arab Maghreb Union (AMU) for North Africa, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) for West Africa, the East African Community (EAC) and the Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) for East Africa, and the Southern African Development Community (SADC) for Southern Africa (Figure 2 and 3), as well as national levels including Morocco, Algeria, Nigeria, Kenya, Egypt, Tunisia, Cameroon, and South Africa (Figure 4 and 5). It examines how shocks to productivity propagate through income channels (income-based Variables) (Figures 2 and 4) and structural economic indicators (Real Economic Variables) (Figures 3 and 5). The results are presented through a comparative lens that captures both inter-regional dynamics and intra-regional diversity.

- **Region-based analysis how shocks to productivity propagate through income channels**

At the regional level, Household Capital Income (YHK) consistently emerges as the most positively responsive indicator (Figure 2). ECOWAS and EAC exhibit the strongest capital income gains, with increases reaching up to 0.26 (26%) under the simulated sequencing shock. These gains suggest that these regions have economic structures that are particularly dominated by capital intensive sectors such as extractives and manufacturing that may absorb more capital enabling them to rapidly integrate technology-led capital productivity gains and further increase YHK (McMillan et al., 2014). By contrast, AMU and SADC record more muted improvements, likely due to slower capital accumulation by less capitalistic industries and lower ease of substitution between labour and capital in these economies (Newfarmer et al., 2018).

Household Labor Income (YHL) declines in all regions, with ECOWAS and UMA showing the most severe losses. These findings indicate a growing divergence between capital accumulation and labor compensation, an issue widely discussed in the literature on technological diffusion in low- and middle-income countries (Rodrik, 2016). This erosion of labor income may reflect a capital-biased productivity in these economies, particularly in sequencing-exposed sectors where technological advances may replace labor or intensify capital use (Brooks et al., 2014; McMillan et al., 2014).

Disposable Household Income (YDH) and Household Total Income (YH) show only marginal gains, while Government Income (YG) declines notably in CEDEAO across scenarios, suggesting a contraction in fiscal revenues despite higher Productions (XS) (Moore et al., 2021). Income from the Rest-of-the-World (YROW) increases slightly in AMU and SADC (Figure 2), likely reflecting remittance inflows and improved terms of trade in export-dominated sectors (African Development Bank, 2022; Ratha et al., 2023).

Shifting to structural responses, Composite Capital Rental Rate (RC) increases across all regions, with ECOWAS (0.310) and ECA (0.280) recording the strongest gains under the high-intensity scenario. This implies that increased capital income and Total Production (XS) have translated into stronger domestic demand (Figure 2). In contrast, Composite Wage Rate (WC) declined across all regions, once again most significantly in AMU (-0.186) and ECOWAS (-0.184), indicating widespread wage compression. Composite Capital Demand (KDC) rises modestly in AMU, ECOWAS, and SADC, while Composite Labor Demand (LDC) contracts most notably in AMU and ECOWAS. In contrast, EAC is the only region to show a consistent increase in labor demand. These patterns reaffirm skewed capital-labor dynamics under sequencing-driven productivity shocks.

These results reveal that capital-deepening processes dominate as a consequence of the sequencing-induced productivity shock, with positive impact on output and income received by households but not in employment. Consequently, economic inequality may widen in the absence of compensatory labor policies. This underscores the need for more effective and adaptive labour policies and social protection schemes to redistribute gains more equitably (African Development Bank, 2019).

Figure 2. Genome sequencing of African biodiversity will have a significant effect on income-based variables across African Regional Economic Communities (RECs). The map shows regional effects concerning Income-based Variables under genetic sequencing-induced productivity shock. The figure presents heatmaps associated with percentage change in income-related variables across

eight African Regional Economic Communities (RECs): Arab Maghreb Union (AMU) (brown), Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) (blue), Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) (purple), East African Community (EAC) (dark green), Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA) (pink), Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS) (light green) and Southern African Development Community (SADC) (Khaki) and Community of Sahel-Saharan States (CEN-SAD) (yellow) as displayed on the map of Africa (see also Table 2). This followed the modelled introduction of biodiversity genome sequencing technologies. For each of the RECs, the associated heatmap show columns which presents three intervention scenarios of increasing intensity, denoted by asterisks: * (low), ** (moderate), and *** (high) (see also Figure S1). Each scenario corresponds to an escalating Total Factor Productivity (TFP) gain in agricultural sectors—5%, 10%, and 15%, respectively—combined with rising Capital Share Parameters (β) and Elasticity of Substitution (ES) (σ) (see Table 1 for definition of terms and Figure S1 for more details). The rows list the income components analysed: Household Capital Income (*YHK*), Household Labor Income (*YHL*), Disposable Household Income (*YDH*), Household Total Income (*YH*), Government Income (*YG*), and Rest-of-the-World total Income (*YROW*) (see Table 1 for definition of terms). All values are expressed as percentage deviations from the Business-as-usual (BAU) scenario assuming unchanged TFP, input shares, and ES. Heatmap color intensity reflects the magnitude of change, with darker blue indicating larger positive values (income gains), and lighter yellow tones representing stronger negative values (income losses).

Figure 3. The simulation shows that the genome sequencing of African biodiversity will have a significant effect on structural economic variables across African Regional Economic Communities (RECs). The map shows regional effects of structural Real Economic variables under genome sequencing-induced productivity shock. This figure presents the percentage changes in key structural macroeconomic indicators across eight African Regional Economic Communities (RECs): Arab Maghreb Union (AMU) (brown), Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) (blue), Economic Community of West African

States (ECOWAS) (purple), East African Community (EAC) (dark green), Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA) (pink), Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS) (light green) and Southern African Development Community (SADC) (Khaki) and Community of Sahel-Saharan States (CEN-SAD) (yellow) as displayed on the map of Africa (see also Table 2). This is in response to the simulated adoption of genetic sequencing technologies in biological diversity. The associated heatmap for each REC columns presents three intervention scenarios of increasing intensity, denoted by asterisks: * (low), ** (moderate), and *** (high) (see also Figure S2). These correspond to 5%, 10%, and 15% increases in Total Factor Productivity (TFP) in biological diversity, combined with rising Capital Share Parameters (β) and input substitution elasticities (ES) (σ), reflecting overall technological progress, improved capital relative efficiency, and the easiness with which capital can substitute for labour. The rows include ten structural indicators tracked in the PEP-w-t model: Household Consumption (C), Intermediate Consumption (CI), Composite Capital Demand (KDC), Composite Labour Demand (LDC), the Intermediate Consumption Price Index (PCI), Unit Cost of Production (PP), the Composite Capital Rental Rate (RC), Value Added (VA), the Composite Labor Wage Rate (WC), and Total Productions (XS) (see Table 1 for definition of terms). The values represent percentage variations relative to the reference (Business-as-usual, BAU) scenario, which assumes an economy without shocks. The color intensity in the heatmap reflects the magnitude and direction of the variation: darker khaki tones indicate larger positive variations, while white tones represent more pronounced negative variations.

- **Country-based analysis how shock to productivity propagate through structural economic indicators**

At the national level (Figure 4), Nigeria exhibits the strongest Household Capital Income (YHK) and Government Income (YG) gains, reflecting its capital-intensive economy centered on oil and large-scale services (Adekunle, 2025). However, it also records the steepest labor income decline, indicating jobless growth. The decoupling between capital and labor in Nigeria exemplifies the risks of overreliance on extractive sectors without parallel investment in labor-intensive activities (Ajakaiye et al., 2015).

Tunisia stands out with well-balanced performance—robust gains in YHK, YG, and YDH, with moderate losses in YHL. This may be due to a diversified economic structure, relatively efficient public institutions, and strong ties to European markets (OECD, 2022). Kenya demonstrates robust responsiveness in capital income, but also suffers sharp labor income losses, pointing to structural vulnerabilities in informal labor markets and uneven benefit distribution (Kiringai & Sanchez Puerta, 2016).

South Africa presents relatively flat results across most indicators, reflecting structural rigidities and subdued responsiveness to external shocks. Modest capital and fiscal gains are offset by persistent labor market constraints, which continue to suppress employment elasticity.

In Egypt, substantial government income gains are observed, but the overall pattern is dampened by state-heavy sectoral dynamics that absorb capital gains without diffusing them broadly through labor markets. This contributes to subdued responsiveness in household-level outcomes and deepening labor income losses under intensified shocks.

Morocco shows moderate improvements across all income indicators, suggesting a more stable, albeit slower, adjustment process, likely supported by ongoing reforms in agri-industry and green energy (African Development Bank, 2022). Cameroon exhibits minimal response, reinforcing its characterization as a low-integration, low-dynamic economy (World Bank, 2024).

The structural variables across countries and sectors provide deeper insight into the transmission channels of the sequencing-induced productivity shock (Figure 5). Nigeria shows a substantial decrease in the Composite Capital Rental Rate (RC), especially in agriculture, biodiversity and services and moderate increases in Total Productions (XS). Composite Capital Demand (KDC) rises sharply in crops, reflecting sequencing-driven investment intensification. These gains are reinforced by strong improvements in Intermediate Consumption (CI) and Value Added (VA) across key sectors. Price Index of Intermediate Consumption (PCI) also increases modestly in

vehicles and energy, indicating limited but positive household-level spillovers (Castro & Jiménez-Rodríguez, 2025). However, these advances are offset by sharp declines in Composite Labor Demand (LDC) and Composite Labor Wage Rate (WC), particularly in light manufacturing, utilities, and energy-intensive sectors.

This adjustment pattern—characterized by gains in RC, CI, and VA, and losses in LDC and WC—is mirrored across most countries, though with varying intensity. While the sharpest losses are concentrated in capital-heavy sectors, broader labor and wage contractions are evident across the economy, reflecting a capital-deepening trajectory with weak employment creation (Alvarez-Cuadrado et al., 2018).

Agriculture, biodiversity and services, particularly transport and communication, consistently register the strongest structural gains. In contrast, manufacturing and utilities experience the steepest contractions in labor and wage indicators, most visibly in Tunisia, Algeria, and South Africa, where dependence on capital- and import-intensive industrial sectors amplifies sequencing-induced dislocations. Algeria's hydrocarbon dependence further restricts labor and capital responsiveness, limiting the absorptive capacity of technological change (Dahmani & Gherbi, 2025).

Morocco, Kenya, and Nigeria stand out for their broader sectoral diversification, which allows for more balanced adjustments. Morocco, in particular, leverages a diversified capital base and ongoing manufacturing expansion to reap structural gains with only moderate labour losses, especially in utilities. Kenya similarly balances biodiversity and service gains with modest labor displacement. By contrast, South Africa and Tunisia, relatively reliant on industrial sectors, register strong contractions in both capital investment and labor use, exposing their vulnerability to global value chain shocks. Egypt maintains overall macroeconomic stability due to structural insulation and domestic orientation (El Husseiny, 2023), but this same rigidity suppresses dynamic gains, with flat trends across most structural variables.

These findings underscore a broader pattern: countries with adaptive, multi-sectoral production systems—notably Morocco, Kenya, and Nigeria—demonstrate stronger resilience and structural flexibility under sequencing shocks. In contrast, countries with narrower industrial bases or energy dependence exhibit deeper dislocations, particularly in employment and capital demand, confirming earlier research on the importance of economic diversification in absorbing technological change (Rijkers et al., 2014; *Trade and Development Report 2023*, 2024).

Figure 4: Genome sequencing of African biodiversity will have irregular income-based effects across and within African countries. The figure shows country-level effects of income-based variables under a genetic sequencing-induced productivity shock across eight African economies. The heatmap captures percentage changes in core income variables for eight African countries: Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Egypt, Nigeria, Cameroon, South Africa and Kenya with their localities presented on a map of Africa. This is in response to simulated agricultural and biodiversity productivity shocks induced by genetic sequencing. Rows associated with each country includes five income indicators: Household Capital Income (*YHK*), Household Labor Income (*YHL*), Disposable Household Income (*YDH*), Government Income (*YG*), and Rest-of-the-World total Income (*YROW*) (see Table 1 for definition of terms), each shown under three columns of intervention scenarios with increasing intensity, denoted by asterisks: * (low), ** (moderate), and *** (high) (see also Figure S3). The Y-axis lists individual countries. All values represent percentage deviations from a business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario, which assumes unchanged productivity, technology, and elasticity. Heatmap color intensity reflects the direction and magnitude of change: darker green indicates stronger income gains, while pale yellow to orange indicates income losses.

Figure 5: Genome sequencing of African biodiversity will have irregular structural effects across and within African countries. The diagram shows structural variable (Real Economic Variables) heatmap for selected African countries under genome sequencing shock. The figure illustrates the percentage change in ten structural economic indicators across thirteen sectors. The heat maps associated with each of the countries show its response to the simulated productivity shock introduced by agricultural and biodiversity genome sequencing. The aggregate variables included are: Household Consumption (C), Intermediate Consumption (CI), Composite Capital Demand (KDC), Composite Labour Demand (LDC), the Intermediate Consumption Price Index (PCI), Unit Cost of Production (PP), the Composite Capital Rental Rate (RC), Value Added (VA), the Composite Labor Wage Rate (WC), and Total Production (XS) (see Table 1 for definition of terms). The heatmap was generated for each of the sub-categories, which were applied to each. The columns show three intervention scenarios of increasing intensity, denoted by asterisks: * (low), ** (moderate), and *** (high) (see also Figure S4). All values represent percentage deviations from a business-as-usual (BAU) scenario without any change in TFP, in capital share parameter, and in the elasticity of substitution of capital to labour (see Table 1 for definition of terms). Green tones indicate sectoral gains, while red tones reflect declines, highlighting highly heterogeneous sectoral responses to the shock across countries and intensities.

Production, income and economy-wide effects

The general equilibrium analysis reveals a coherent and internally consistent picture of how investments in sequencing capacity propagate through African economies, combining sectoral production adjustments (QP variables/Real Economic Variables) with income redistribution (Y variables) (Figure 6 - 9, S5 - S7) (see also Text Box 1). The analysis of volume variables (real sphere) demonstrates that sequencing-induced productivity gains initially materialize through adjustments in biodiversity, manufacturing and services, with notable heterogeneity reflecting differences in production structure, factor intensities and degrees of trade integration. The large economies — such as Nigeria, South Africa, and Egypt — exhibit widespread and symmetrical positive responses across several sectors, consistent with greater productive diversification and agglomeration effects (Krugman, 1991). In contrast, smaller economies display more concentrated, weak, and asymmetrical sectoral adjustments, symptomatic of less integrated productive structures and narrower supply linkages (Figure 6 - 9). The analysis of volume variables (real sphere) further highlights the role of transmission channels and sectoral linkage: downstream manufacturing and service activities amplify upstream productivity gains, while energy and capital-intensive sectors may experience compensating retractions, consistent with factor allocation in a general equilibrium setting. These patterns underline that the economic impact of biodiversity genome sequencing investments is not limited to research or primary production alone, but extends throughout the entire economy, reshaping relative prices and resource allocation.

Complementing this production-side view, the income-based variables analysis (Figure 9) clarifies how these gains are ultimately distributed across economic agents. Changes in Government Income (YG) are substantial, particularly in large economies, reflecting increased tax revenue generated by expanded economic activity. Household Disposal Income (YDH) and Household Total Income (YH) respond more modestly, illustrating the decrease of labour demand. In contrast, factor-income channels reveal more pronounced adjustments: Household Capital Income (YHK) generally increases, while Household Labor Income (YHL) declines in several countries, capturing the substitution toward capital and skill intensive activities induced by sequencing-driven technological progress (Figure 9).

More importantly, the calibrated benefit-cost ratios integrate both real economic variables (quantity-prices variables) and income-based variable effects into a single economy-wide metric (Figure 6). Anchored on an independently estimated Moroccan BCR of 3.29 (Hayah et al., 2025), cross country BCRs range from below 1 unity in small economies, such as Cameroon, to above 20 in Nigeria, reflecting the interaction of scale effects and structural readiness to absorb innovation. These

results underscore that sequencing investments yield systemic economic returns, not merely sector gains. The combined evidence from production, income and calibrated benefit metrics points to sequencing as transformative infrastructure investment. Its benefits arise through complex supply-chain propagation and institutional redistribution mechanisms, highlighting the importance of coordinated policy frameworks to maximize inclusive and sustainable returns, particularly within a perspective linking agriculture, environmental resilience and human welfare (see also Text Box 1).

Figure 6. Country-level calibrated benefit–cost ratios (BCRs) for a 20 million USD genomic sequencing investment. Bars report unitless BCRs derived from PEP-w-t recursive dynamic general-equilibrium simulations and calibrated using Morocco’s independently estimated BCR of 3.29 (Hayah et al., 2025). For each country, the BCR is computed from an aggregate economy-wide model response (Δ_j^{model}) that combines quantity-price-based value changes across production and factor-use blocks with changes in nominal income flows as defined in the methods (Eqs. 1-6). Aggregate model responses are converted to monetary benefits by proportional calibration relative to Morocco and divided by the fixed investment cost to obtain BCRs (methods, Eqs. 7-12). Cross-country differences therefore reflect how national economic structures transmit and amplify the same sequencing-related productivity shock, rather than differences in investment size, which is held constant. Countries shown are Algeria, South Africa, Tunisia, Nigeria, Morocco, Kenya, Egypt, and Cameroon.

Sectoral fingerprints by country (normalized aggregated Δ Value across XS, CI, C, LDC, KDC)

Figure 7: Multi-country sectoral fingerprints of the genomics productivity shock (normalized shape comparison). Radar plots depict each country's sectoral response profile ("fingerprint") based on the aggregated quantity-price value changes ($\Delta Value$) across the *XS*, *CI*, *C*, *LDC*, *KDC*. For each sector i and country j , the value change is computed following equations 1-3 in the method section, using the corresponding price matrices (PP for *XS* and *C*; PCI for *CI*; WC for *LDC*; RC for *KDC*). Sectoral contributions are then summed across QP variables to obtain the aggregate sector-level impact $\Delta Total_{ij}$ per country. To emphasize shock propagation structure rather than magnitude, each country's sectoral profile is normalized by its maximum absolute sectoral contribution (max-absolute scaling), such that radar values range from -1 to +1 and are directly comparable across countries. Differences in radar shapes therefore reflect structural differences in how the genomics shock propagates through national production and supply-chain linkages, rather than differences in overall impact size. Panels show: (A) DZA (Algeria), (B) ZAF (South Africa), (C) TUN (Tunisia), (D) NGA (Nigeria), (E) MAR (Morocco), (F) KEN (Kenya), (G) EGY (Egypt), and (H) CMR (Cameroon).

Sectoral contributions by country (aggregated Δ Value across XS, CI, C, LDC, KDC)

Figure 8: Sectorial contributions to the sequencing shock across countries (aggregated quantity-price effects). Each panel reports the sectorial contributions to the general equilibrium response of a sequencing investment for one country. For sector i and country j , bars represent the aggregated quantity-price value change across all the QP variables, computed following equations 1-4 in the method section. Positive (negative) bars indicate sectors that expand (contract) following the shock. Differences across panels reflect country-specific production structures, factor intensities, and inter-sectoral linkages governing the propagation of the effect of the sequencing investment within each economy. Country panels are labeled A–H for visual consistency with the sectoral fingerprint figure. A: DZA (Algeria). B: ZAF (South Africa). C: TUN (Tunisia). D: NGA (Nigeria). E: MAR (Morocco). F: KEN (Kenya). G: EGY (Egypt). H: CMR (Cameroun).

Country-level Y-variable responses to sequencing shock (verified deltas)

Figure 9: Country-level responses of income variables to the sequencing shock. Each panel reports changes in institutional income and factor-return components for one country, computed as the difference between post-shock and pre-shock values following equation 5 in the method section. Results are shown for Disposable Household Income (YDH), Government Income (YG), Household Total Income (YH), Household Capital Income (YHK), Household Labor Income (YHL), and Rest-of-the-World total Income ($YROW$). Positive (negative) bars indicate gains (losses) in the corresponding income channel. Together with the quantity-price decomposition, these results illustrate how sequencing-driven productivity gains propagate and affect institutional income distribution and macroeconomic balances in the GTAP framework. A: DZA (Algeria). B: ZAF (South Africa). C: TUN (Tunisia). D: NGA (Nigeria). E: MAR (Morocco). F: KEN (Kenya). G: EGY (Egypt). H: CMR (Cameroun).

Economics of Intellectual Property, Genetic Resources, Digital Sequence Information, and Access and Benefit-Sharing

The legal framework underlying the global governance of genetic resources and Digital Sequence Information (DSI) is shaped by various international treaties or frameworks such as the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (UNEP Convention on Biological Diversity, 2011a), Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-Sharing (UNEP Convention on Biological Diversity, 2011b), Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF) (UNEP Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022, 2024), International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (FAO, 2009), Agreement on the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Marine Biodiversity of Areas beyond National Jurisdiction (United Nations, 2023), and the World Intellectual Property Organisation (WIPO) Treaty on Intellectual Property, Genetic Resources and Associated Traditional Knowledge (WIPO, 2024).

Globally, researchers and innovators are increasingly using Intellectual Property (IP) rights to protect their work (Hill et al., 2025; Pires & Ferreira, 2025). These rights influence, among others, how countries share data and benefits (Borthakur, 2023), especially in the evolving landscape of AI (Koellner, 2025; Poddar & Rao, 2024) and DSI (Katee et al., 2024). For example, of the 92 countries with ABS policies relevant to microorganisms, 74 restricts access to these pathogens and 53 link access to pathogen resources with an obligation to share benefits, while 22 countries have a codified position on DSI with regard to ABS (Ljungqvist et al., 2025).

In Africa, IP rights have existed long before the introduction of western IP laws (de Beer et al., 2018; Lawal-Arowolo, 2015). It is documented that African customary laws protected the rights of the members of the communities (Arowolo, 2019). For example, ancient Egyptians (artisans and craftsmen) used symbols and marks to identify their products (Namfukwe, 2024) while in traditional African societies, stories, music, and art, were passed down from generations to generations, with each community having their unique cultural expressions (Namfukwe, 2024). Despite this, Africa retains significant scope for IP policy innovation and African IP landscape has evolved over this period (de Beer et al., 2018; Dladla, 2025) but several challenges and opportunities persist up until present day (Ajakaye & Lawal, 2025; Munyoro et al., 2025) such as conflicting priorities between colonial era enacted IP laws and African IP interests (de Beer et al., 2018), interoperability of IP with AI (Okorie, 2025), IP versus Open Science (Adaji & Abdulrauf, 2024), IP versus Access and Benefit-Sharing (Ezeanya, 2013; Motari et al., 2021, 2021), fragmentation of the national and regional African IP landscape (Adebola, 2020), and limited awareness of IP rights across Africa (see Figure 10 and S8.1). Only 15% of African countries have established national IP offices (Namfukwe, 2024) whilst several African countries are also members of the regional IP frameworks such as African Regional Intellectual Property Organization and African Intellectual Property Organization (Namfukwe, 2024). At the continental level, the AfCFTA's Protocol on Intellectual

Property Rights aims to harmonise the various IP frameworks across Africa (Ogbodo, 2025).

We highlight results of the first survey-based overviews of the IP landscape for biodiversity genetic resources and DSI across Africa (Figure 10A and Figure S8). This inquiry reveals a complex interplay between scientific capacity, access to infrastructure, and IP awareness and benefit-sharing (see Additional texts S1 in supplementary information for details). While African researchers demonstrate high levels of engagement in biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics research (Figure S8.1), the results underscore persistent structural and governance gaps that limit equitable access, protection, and benefit realization from genetic resources and DSI (Figure S8.4) (see also Text Box 2).

A

The African DSI & IP Landscape: A Journey from Context to Action

B

Figure 10: Survey respondents' awareness and behavior towards intellectual property laws and trade secrets in the biodiversity genetic resources and DSI reveal that IP knowledge is not directly proportional with willingness to share DSI data. A: Alluvial plot showing respondents' self-reported knowledge towards IP policies and their current and future intentions of generating digital sequence information for either public or permissive use. The spectrum of colors track the respondents' affiliations with institutions or organisations operating within member states of the African Union (Affiliation). Here, the respondents' active and future projects are shown (Project type), their familiarity with digital sequence information (DSI Know.) and IP processes (IP Know.). Included is awareness of policy at the national level, knowledge of how copyright benefits their research outputs (Copyright know.), policies in place at the institutional (Inst. IP) and national-level (Country IP). The respondents also state whether they have technical support (Need skills) as well

as the personal capabilities to carry out genome-related projects to completion (Has skills). Their preference on how to use and re-use the data they generate is also shown (Access Pref.). Next, the respondents share their sentiment towards how an increase of IP and trade secret awareness would lead to increased DSI sharing (Share IP and Share TM, respectively). The last four columns relate to the respondents activity in terms of active applications towards patents (Patents), Trademarks (Trademarks) as well as respondents that report possessing trademarks (Has TM) and their general commercialisation strategy (Commercialisation) (see supplementary Figure S8 for more details). This figure was generated in R v 4.4.1 primarily using the package ggaluvial v 0.21.5 (Brunson, 2020; Brunson & Read, 2023). **B:** The violin plot (B) shows an aggregated knowledge score assigned to questions where knowledge was indicated by respondents (and between respondents) that indicate that they share data on public repositories, which was compared against those that did not. In this plot, respondents that declared that their research does not produce digital sequence information were omitted (see supplementary Figure S8 for more details). The figure was generated using R v 4.4.1 primarily using the package ggplot2 v 4.0.1 (Wickham, 2016).

Text Boxes

Text Box 1

Shock transmission channels

The sector-country heatmap (Figure S7) of $\Delta Total_{ij}$ reveals a highly heterogeneous pattern of shock propagation across both sectors and countries. In all countries, a small number of sectors account for the bulk of the response, while several others display near-zero changes, indicating limited direct involvement in the genomic-driven adjustment. Energy, transport and other services typically show sizable positives or negatives changes, reflecting their central role as upstream inputs and downstream facilitators in the production network.

For Morocco, the sectoral bar plot shows that the sequencing shock is absorbed primarily through a combination of agricultural sectors (e.g. grains, crops, livestock) and service sectors (transport and other services) (Figure 7 and 8, S5 and S7). Positive contributions in these sectors indicate that productivity gains and cost reductions in genomics translate into higher value added along agro-food and service supply chains. At the same time, some manufacturing sectors may exhibit small or even slightly negative responses, suggesting reallocation effects and relative price changes that redirect resources towards more genomics-responsive activities.

In Nigeria, the sectoral profile is more strongly dominated by energy, transport and heavy manufacturing, consistent with a more energy- and resource-intensive production structure (Figure 7 and 8, S5 and S7). Large positive $\Delta Total_{ij}$ values in these sectors imply that sequencing-induced productivity improvements in biodiversity and related activities such as agriculture propagate upstream into energy demand and downstream into logistics and processing. This pattern explains why Nigeria emerges with one of the highest calibrated BCRs in the cross-country comparison: its supply chain is structurally well positioned to amplify and transmit genomic gains across multiple high-value sectors (Figure 6).

Taken together, the heatmap and country-specific sectoral profiles demonstrate that the shock does not act uniformly across the economy (Figure 7 and 8, S5 and S7). Instead, it follows the pre-existing production and input-output linkages: in some countries, gains are concentrated in primary production and services, while in others they are transmitted through energy and industrial backbones. These structural differences in supply-chain propagation help to rationalize the observed variation in calibrated BCRs across countries.

Text Box 2

Significance of survey on Intellectual Property (IP), Genetic Resources, Digital Sequence Information, and Access and Benefit-Sharing

We carried out a survey to understand the landscape, practices, opportunities, and gaps that exist regarding IP protections and rights for biodiversity genetic resources and DSI across Africa to help shape strategies for equitable access, benefit-sharing, acknowledgements, recognitions, and innovations across Africa while fostering stronger alignment between DSI, biodiversity governance and IP systems (see also Method section).

The perception that increased patenting and IP awareness could promote greater data sharing is particularly noteworthy (Figure S8.4), as it challenges the assumption that IP necessarily restricts openness. Instead, it suggests that African researchers may view IP as a mechanism for secure sharing, provided attribution, recognition and benefit sharing safeguards are in place. Initially, the survey hypothesis assumed that reduced IP awareness would lead to more reluctance but the result shows it is non-significant ($p = 0.16$) (Figure 10B), suggesting that African researchers, irrespective of their knowledge of IP laws, are *willing* to share DSI (Figure 10B).

Overall, the findings suggest that equitable access to genetic resources and DSI in Africa remains aspirational rather than realized (see Additional texts S1 in supplementary information for details). Current IP frameworks provide partial protection but fall short of enabling consistent benefit sharing and commercialization as evidenced by a majority of the respondents (Figure S8.7). Nevertheless, the strong interest in IP (Figure S8.3 - S8.5), support for disclosure requirements (Figure S8.4), and recognition of equity (Figure S8.8) concerns indicate readiness for reform. With coordinated continental action, improved institutional capacity, and integration of IP into biodiversity governance, Africa has the potential to shift from a primarily data-providing role to that of a value-creating and agenda-setting actor in global biodiversity genomics.

To situate this analysis within the wider research landscape, we examined thematic emphasis and international collaboration patterns in genomics and bioinformatics. Figure S9A indicates that genetics serves as a central research domain, with frequent connections to agriculture, biodiversity conservation and computer science, reflecting the applied orientation of this work toward food systems, environmental management and data-intensive methods. Figure S9B illustrates the collaborative dimension of this research, showing dense and sustained co-authorship links between African researchers and partners in Europe, North America and Asia, with heavy collaboration recorded between South Africa and partners outside the African continent. The resulting scheme is one of a research field that is simultaneously grounded in local priorities and embedded within global scientific networks.

Text Box 3

Re-caliberating and reconfiguring African economies

This study also demonstrates that genome sequencing, when applied to African biodiversity systems, offers substantial macroeconomic benefits, particularly in enhancing capital productivity and trade efficiency. However, these gains are not uniformly distributed. Many regions experience a decline in labor income, reflecting deeper structural rigidities and weak absorptive capacities. The analysis reveals significant inter- and intra- regional disparities, emphasizing that one-size-fits-all strategies are inadequate. Instead, tailored, evidence-based policy frameworks are required to ensure that technological progress translates into inclusive economic transformation. By integrating genome sequencing in an environment with better governance, tailored labor-enhancing strategies, and regional coordination mechanisms, African economies can harness this innovation not only for productivity gains but also for equity, resilience, and sustainable development.

African genomics and bioinformatics is grounded in local priorities like agriculture but remains heavily reliant on global partnerships. While these networks are robust, the continent primarily still serves as a data provider because current IP frameworks fail to ensure equitable benefit sharing. Transitioning to a "value-creating" role requires coordinated continental action and the integration of IP into biodiversity governance. Clear rules on attribution and protection can strengthen incentives for local innovation and more deliberate risk-taking. Over time, such safeguards enable African states to capture greater economic value from DSI, while supporting sustained growth and scientific sovereignty.

The introduction of genome sequencing technologies into African biodiversity represents a pivotal opportunity to enhance productivity, accelerate structural transformation, and strengthen food systems resilience. However, as evidenced by our macroeconomic simulations, this technological disruption is characterized by asymmetrical outcomes, most notably, substantial gains in capital income (YHK) offsetted by consistent declines in labor income (YHL). Such divergence, if unaddressed, risks exacerbating socioeconomic inequalities and undermining inclusive development. To translate these bio-innovations into equitable and sustainable outcomes, a coordinated suite of policy responses tailored to the specific institutional, structural, and demographic realities of African economies is imperative. A foremost priority is the reform of labor markets. The widespread contraction in labor income across all modeled regions, particularly ECOWAS and UMA, signals weak labor absorption capacity amidst capital-driven growth. Governments must respond with structural reforms that elevate the employability and the skills of the workforce. Strategic investments in biodiversity related innovations such as

biodiversity conservation, agro-technological training, vocational education, and the transition from informal to formal employment—especially in agro-processing, climate-smart activities, biodiversity conservation, and agriculture, and rural logistics—can enhance labor responsiveness and ensure that technological progress does not harm workers.

Text Box 4

Policy recommendations

We make a number of policy-related recommendations: First, investment in sequencing should be treated as a means to establish a strategic economic infrastructure comparable to energy, transport or digital systems. Their benefits accrue systematically through supply chains and institutional channels, rather than remaining confined to research laboratories.

Second, countries with high calibrated BCRs should prioritize rapid scaling and regional leadership in sequencing platforms while countries with low BCRs should focus on complementary investments such as human capital development, data governance, and downstream analytical capacities to improve absorptive capacity and maximize returns.

Third, given the observed shift toward capital income, sequencing investment must be accompanied by inclusive labour and skills policies, including training, scaling and integration of genomics into biodiversity, agricultural extension, veterinary services and public health systems.

Finally, policymakers should adopt integrated evaluation frameworks, similar to the calibrated BCR approach used here, that explicitly account for both production and income effects, ensuring that sequencing investments are assessed not only for efficiency but also for distributional and sustainability outcomes. Sequencing is not merely a scientific tool but a transformational development lever, capable of generating sustained economic, fiscal, and societal returns when embedded within coherent, cross-sectoral policy strategies.

For countries like Nigeria and Kenya, which demonstrated pronounced capital responsiveness but limited labor inclusivity, fiscal redistribution becomes a critical policy lever. A portion of the capital gains catalyzed by sequencing technologies should be mobilized through progressive taxation and targeted reinvestment into public goods—namely, healthcare, education, transport, and digital infrastructure in rural and peri-urban areas. Such redistribution not only cushions vulnerable populations from exclusion but also generates secondary economic multipliers by stimulating domestic demand and enabling smallholder participation in value chains. The analysis also underscores the significance of domestic demand, particularly in

ECOWAS and CEA, where Composite Capital Rental Rate (RC) and Intermediate Consumption (CI) surged. Policymakers in these regions should leverage this momentum by prioritizing the development of agro-industrial corridors, enhancing SME competitiveness, and operationalizing the AfCFTA to lower intraregional trade barriers. These measures can serve to internalize productivity gains, stabilize factor markets, and promote inclusive job creation.

However, significant intra-regional disparities—such as those between Morocco and Algeria or between Senegal and Nigeria—caution against overly homogenized policy prescriptions. While regional blocs such as ECOWAS, UMA, and SADC can serve as coordination platforms, policy actions must be modular and country-specific. Morocco, with its diversified industrial base and renewable energy capacity, may pursue deepened technological integration. Algeria, in contrast, must first prioritize economic diversification and institutional reforms to increase sequencing absorption capacity. Countries displaying structural fragility—such as Cameroon, Mozambique, and to a lesser extent Egypt—should be guided by comprehensive sequencing readiness assessments. These should evaluate governance quality, fiscal space, trade infrastructure, and institutional absorptive capacity before scaling up genomic technologies. In contexts where foundational capacities are limited, emphasis should be placed on first building enabling environments through reforms in macroeconomic policy, digital infrastructure, and agricultural extension services.

Finally, a critical cross-cutting recommendation is the establishment of adaptive governance systems for bio-innovation. Policymaking must be iterative, data-driven, and anchored in continuous feedback from real-world pilot programs. National statistical agencies and regional research hubs, in partnership with biodiversity research institutions and innovation platforms, should monitor real-time changes in income distribution, labor dynamics, and sectoral outputs. This would enable course correction, risk mitigation, and the design of context-aware interventions aligned with long-term development goals.

Conclusion, recommendation, and look ahead

This study provides a comprehensive general-equilibrium assessment of the impact of investments in biodiversity genomic sequencing capacity on the sectoral and aggregate levels with a special focus on redistributive consequences using the GTAP CGEM. The scrutinizing of QP variables (XS, CI, C, LDC, KDC) and Y variables (YDH, YG, YH, YHK, YHL, YROW), provides evidence that sequencing investments generate economy-wide benefits that extend far beyond the research sector, reshaping production structures, supply chains, and income distribution patterns.

On the production side, sequencing-induced productivity gains propagate through the entire economy, particularly in agriculture, biodiversity, manufacturing, and service sectors, with substantial heterogeneity across countries. Large and diversified economies exhibit broad-based positive responses, while smaller or less diversified economies display more concentrated sectoral effects. These findings confirm that the economic payoff from sequencing depends not only on the magnitude of the investment but critically on structural readiness, including sectoral composition, factor intensities, and trade integration (see also Text Box 3 and 4).

On the income side, the nominal variable analysis shows that the gains from sequencing are distributed unevenly across institutional agents. Government revenues increase consistently, enhancing fiscal space for public investment, while household disposable income responds more modestly. Importantly, factor-income adjustments reveal a tendency toward capital income expansion and relative labor income contraction, reflecting the high skill- and capital-biased nature of sequencing-driven technological change. These dynamics emphasize that the economic benefits of genomics are real but not automatically inclusive (see also Text Box 3 and 4).

By integrating both production and income channels, the calibrated benefit–cost ratios (BCRs) provide a holistic measure of economic returns. Anchored on Morocco’s independently estimated BCR, the resulting cross-country BCRs range from below unity to above 20, highlighting stark differences in capacity to absorb and leverage sequencing investments. Crucially, these BCRs already incorporate both quantity–prices and income based effects, capturing the full general-equilibrium impact rather than partial or sector-specific outcomes (see also Text Box 3 and 4).

To the best of our knowledge, the study reported in this paper represents the first integrated analysis to simultaneously examine the predicted linkages between DSI generation and use within the combined context of ABS, IP, and the economics of biodiversity as well as its overlaps with KMGBF objectives, including Target 19, which calls for mobilising at least US\$200 billion per year for biodiversity by 2030. By linking biodiversity sequencing to measurable economic outcomes, this work reframes DSI not only as a scientific resource but as a relevant asset or infrastructure that sustains all activities that contribute to biodiversity preservation.

Beyond its immediate findings, the current paper initiates the “AfricaBP Biodiversity Genomics and Bioinformatics for Social Impact Initiatives”, a coordinated, multi stage programme designed to integrate biodiversity genomics, bioinformatics, data science, and AI to inform meaningful, visible and measurable social impacts across Africa such as in economic, One Health, and logistics systems through the provision of quantitative and qualitative data and information. To kickstart this social impact initiatives, the present study launches the African Gene2Economy Initiative as the economic pillar of this agenda, implemented through phased analyses progressing from the Genomes2Economy pilot (this paper) to increasingly resolved

GenomeTaxa2Economy (moderate taxa-level resolution of quantifiable economic impacts without biological depth) and GenomeTaxaFunctions2Economy assessments (high resolution of quantifiable economic impact with emphasis on biological depth), including interfaces with customs such as GenomeTaxaFunctions2Customs (deeper sectoral resolution with customs, clearing/forwarding, and levies/duties with emphasis on biological depth) and trade under AfCFTA. To operationalise these analyses, AfricaBP is establishing a continental portal platform coordinated by Mohammed V University in Rabat, enabling country-specific assessments of economic impacts from sequencing African biodiversity.

AfricaBP aims to engage the African Union, AfCFTA, the African Development Bank, RECs, and national economic and STI agencies to embed these insights within policy, economics, and trade. Fast-track clearing and forwarding services, including duty-free custom imports, for scientific equipment, technologies, reagents and consumables, holds the key to drive up scientific research and innovation as well as trade and investments across the African life science sector. The African Union, in 2007, suggested that African countries need to spend 1% of GDP on research and development to better contribute to global science and innovation (IISD, 2007). However, as of 2023, African countries contribute an average of 0.45% of GDP well below the global average of 1.7% (United Nations Secretary-General, 2025). In our view, African countries participating in such arrangements for custom duty-free and fast-track clearing and forwarding services for scientific equipment, technologies, consumables, and reagents, could have that counted towards their 1% of GDP allocated to research and development. Such GenomeTaxaFunctions2Customs could provide the baseline quantitative information required by African policymakers and STI and economic agencies.

Method

The CGE model used here was augmented with natural capital, technical capacity, and land. Here, we describe the methods (see also data and code availability sections) employed for the various analysis discussed, namely:

1. *Region-based and country-based modelling and analysis*: The modeling and analysis framework used to evaluate the macroeconomic impacts of introducing genome-sequencing technologies into African biodiversity employ the PEP-w-t recursive dynamic CGE model (version 4.0) (Robichaud et al., 2013). This model is a multi-region, multi-sector computable general equilibrium framework widely applied to assess trade, productivity, and policy shocks (Aguiar et al., 2022; Hertel, 1997), and it is calibrated on the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) 11 Database. For this study, the simulations were conducted at both regional and national levels. At the regional level, we

grouped countries into major African economic-regional blocs using recognized economic communities (RECs): AMU, IGAD, ECOWAS, EAC, COMESA, ECCAS, SADC, and CEN-SAD (see Table 2). At the national level, simulations were performed for key countries: Morocco (MAR), Nigeria (NGA), Kenya (KEN), Egypt (EGY), Algeria (DZA), South Africa (ZAF), Tunisia (TUN), and Cameroon (CMR).

We began by constructing a business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario, which was developed based on the historical data and projections of Fouré, Bénassy-Quéré and Fontagné (2012) (Fouré et al., 2012). This scenario incorporates exogenous growth rates for labor supply and for other variables, calibrated savings rates, and total factor productivity trends. The BAU scenario was calibrated on the GTAP 11 Data Base, once calibrated, it served as the counterfactual against which the sequencing-productivity shock was compared. (Aguiar et al., 2022; Hertel, 1997).

Three policy scenarios were analyzed to evaluate the impacts of agricultural productivity improvements combined with structural reforms. Production-side effects were tracked through changes in sectoral output (XS), value added (VA), and intermediate consumption (CI). Factor market adjustments were measured via capital demand (KDC), labor demand (LDC), rental rates (RC), and wage rates (WC). Price transmission was analyzed through intermediate consumption price indices (PCI) and unit production costs (PP). Income distribution effects were assessed using household income components (YH , YDH , YHK , YHL), government revenue (YG), and external balances ($YROW$) (Robichaud et al., 2013) (see also Additional texts S5 in supplementary information) (see also Table 1 for full definitions).

The intervention scenario introduced a productivity shock reflecting the adoption of genome sequencing as proposed in empirical literature. This includes: (1) a 5% increase in total factor productivity (TFP) $A_{z,t}^{VA}$ in agricultural and/or biodiversity sectors; (2) an increase in the capital share parameter (β) to reflect its improved relative efficiency; and (3) a 0.1-0.3 increase in substitution elasticities ($\sigma = \frac{1}{(1-\rho)}$), to account for the enhanced flexibility of input use enabled by precision agriculture.

The PEP-w-t model's nested Constant Elasticity of Substitution (CES) production function enabled us to evaluate how these technological advances influence the allocation of labor and capital. Sensitivity analyses were also conducted to test the robustness of findings under alternative elasticity adjustments and to isolate the effects of the 5% TFP increase from other model dynamics.

We visualized our scenario results through intensity heatmaps to reveal comparative economic impacts. Cross-country heatmaps compared responses across the eight African economies, showing where agricultural productivity gains generated the strongest ripple effects. Cross-sector heatmaps illustrated how different industries were affected by the shocks. Color intensities represented the magnitude of changes in production, employment, incomes, and costs, allowing immediate visual identification of which economies and sectors benefited most, which faced adjustment pressures, and how structural reforms influenced the distribution of gains across the economic landscape.

2. *Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)*: We report the approaches we used for the CBA which involved data gathering from GTAP database and units, notation delineating, construction of value matrices for XS , CI , C , LDC , and KDC , defining Income variables (YDH , YG , YH , YHK , YHL , $YROW$), aggregation across variables, linking PEP-w-t results to a 20-million USD sequencing investment, and proportional calibration of model deltas.

GTAP database and units

The analysis was conducted using results from the PEP-w-t CGE model, calibrated on the GTAP 11 Database. In GTAP, all monetary values are expressed in millions of current U.S. dollars. In an intermediate preprocessing step, these monetary flows were scaled down by a factor of 10^4 for numerical convenience. Consequently, any GTAP-derived monetary difference (Δ) used in this study is initially expressed in “model units” that are proportional to (million USD / 10^4). For the calibration step (see below), we rely only on relative differences across countries and rescale them using an external cost-benefit benchmark for Morocco. The uniform scaling factor therefore does not affect relative country-level results.

Notation

We index sectors by $i = 1, \dots, I$ and countries (or regions) by $j = 1, \dots, J$. For each quantity-price (QP) variable v (including XS , CI , C , LDC , KDC), the model provides:

- $q_{ij}^{v,0}$: quantity of variable v in sector i and country j before the shock
- $q_{ij}^{v,1}$: quantity of variable v in sector i and country j after the shock
- $p_{ij}^{v,0}$: corresponding price index (PP , PCI , WC , RC) before the shock
- $p_{ij}^{v,1}$: corresponding price index after the shock

For the nominal variables (YDH , YG , YH , YHK , YHL , $YROW$), the model directly reports:

- $Y_j^{y,0}$: income component y in country j before the shock (in model million units)
- $p_j^{y,1}$: income component y in country j after the shock (in model million units)

Construction of value matrices for XS , CI , C , LDC , and LDC

For each QP variable v and sector-country pair (i, j) , the monetary value before and after the sequencing-related technological shock (Scenario 1*) is computed using the quantity-price identity for sector-level variables and their corresponding price indices: XS with PP , CI with PCI , C with PP , LDC with WC , and KDC with RC , as follows:

- $Value_{ij}^{v,0} = q_{ij}^{v,0} \times p_{ij}^{v,0}$ (1)

- $Value_{ij}^{v,1} = q_{i,j}^{v,1} \times p_{ij}^{v,1}$ (2)

Both $Value_{ij}^{v,0}$ and $Value_{ij}^{v,1}$ are in model million units (proportional to million USD / 10^4). The sector-country change in value due to the shock is:

- $\Delta Value_{ij}^v = Value_{ij}^{v,1} - Value_{ij}^{v,0}$ (3)

For each variable v and country j , the total change over all sectors is obtained by summing over i :

- $\Delta Total_{ij} = \sum_{v \in \{XS, CI, C, LDC, KDC\}} \Delta Value_{ij}^v$ (4)

This yields, for each QP variable, a country-level impact $\Delta Value_j^v$ in model million units.

Income variables (YDH , YG , YH , YHK , YHL , $YROW$)

For the income variables, the PEP-w-t/GTAP output directly provides the before- and after-shock values for each country j , without an explicit quantity-price decomposition. For each income component y and country j , we define:

- $\Delta Y_j^y = Y_j^{y,1} - Y_j^{y,0}$ (5)

These differences are also in model million units and represent the change in the corresponding income flow (e.g. household disposable income, government income, household labour income).

Aggregation across variables

For each country j , we construct a single aggregate impact Δ_j^{model} by summing all QP and income contributions:

$$\bullet \Delta_j^{model} = \sum_{v \in QP} \Delta Value_j^v + \sum_{y \in Y} \Delta Y_j^y \quad (6)$$

where “ QP ” denotes the set of quantity-price variables (XS, CI, C, LDC, KDC) and “ Y ” denotes the set of income variables ($YDH, YG, YH, YHK, YHL, YROW$). The resulting Δ_j^{model} is a dimensionless model-consistent measure of the net economic effect of the sequencing shock in country j . It preserves the general equilibrium interactions across sectors and between production, factor incomes, and final demand.

Linking PEP-w-t results to a 20 million USD sequencing investment

The shock (Scenario 1*) is a technological and behavioural perturbation (e.g. total factor productivity and elasticities) and is not directly expressed as an explicit 20 million USD investment. To interpret the model results in terms of an actual sequencing programme, we use an external CBA conducted for Morocco in Hayah et al., 2024 (Hayah et al., 2025). This independent CBA showed that a 20 million USD investment in genome sequencing yields a Benefit–Cost ratio (BCR) of 3.29 for Morocco alone (Hayah et al., 2025), implying a total economic benefit of:

$$\bullet B_{target, MAR} = 3.29 \times 20,000,000 = 65,800,000 \text{ USD} \quad (7)$$

Proportional calibration of model deltas

Morocco is used as an anchor to calibrate the absolute scale of PEP-w-t–derived impacts while preserving their relative cross-country pattern. Let Δ_{MAR}^{model} denote the aggregate model impact for Morocco. We define a calibration factor k (in USD per model unit) such that the model-based benefit for Morocco matches the CBA result:

$$\bullet k \times \Delta_{MAR}^{model} = B_{target, MAR} \quad (8)$$

which implies:

- $k = \frac{B_{target,MAR}}{\Delta_{MAR}^{model}}$ (9)

This factor k is then applied uniformly to all countries j to convert their model deltas into calibrated benefits in USD:

- $Benefit_j = k \times \Delta_j^{model}$ (10)

Calibrated country-level Benefit–Cost ratios

Finally, for each country j , we compute a calibrated BCR by dividing the calibrated benefit by the investment cost $I = 20,000,000 USD$:

- $BCR_j^{calibrated} = \frac{Benefit_j}{I} = \frac{k \times \Delta_j^{model}}{I}$ (11)

Substituting the definition of k yields:

- $BCR_j^{calibrated} = \left(\frac{\Delta_j^{model}}{\Delta_{MAR}^{model}} \right) \times BCR_{MAR}^{external}$ (12)

Thus, the calibrated BCR for any country j is proportional to its model-derived aggregate effect relative to Morocco and anchored to the empirically validated Moroccan BCR. This approach ensures that: (i) the global PEP-w-t/GTAP structure and cross-country ranking are preserved, (ii) absolute benefit magnitudes are consistent with an external economic assessment, and (iii) the resulting BCRs are interpretable as returns on a 20 million USD genomic sequencing investment.

3. *Supply chain impact and sectoral shock propagation*: We report the approaches we used for sector-country value changes for quantity-price variables, heatmap of sectoral shock exposure, Country-specific sectoral profiles, and linkages with calibrated BCRs.

Sector-country value changes for quantity-price variables

To analyse how the sequencing-related shock propagates across production sectors, we focus on the five quantity-price variables XS , CI , C , LDC and KDC . For each variable v and for each sector i in country j , the model provides a before-shock quantity $q_{ij}^{v,0}$, an after-shock quantity $q_{ij}^{v,1}$, and the corresponding before- and after-shock price indices $p_{ij}^{v,0}$ and $p_{ij}^{v,1}$. These prices are taken from the appropriate GTAP price sheets (PP for XS and C , PCI for CI , WC for LDC and RC for KDC).

For each sector-country pair (i, j) and variable v , we reconstruct the monetary value before and after the shock as in equations 1-2. The associated sector-country change in value is computed following equation 3.

These $\Delta Value_{ij}^v$ are expressed in model million units (proportional to million USD up to a common scaling factor, which is handled separately in the calibration step).

Aggregation to sector–country shock exposure

To characterise the total shock received by each sector i in country j , we aggregate across all five quantity-price variables as computed following equation 4.

The resulting matrix $\Delta Total_{ij}$ (with dimensions sectors \times countries) captures the sectoral decomposition of the shock. Positive values indicate sectors that gain value (either through higher quantities, higher prices, or both), whereas negative values indicate sectors that lose value due to reallocation and relative price adjustments.

Heatmap of sectoral shock exposure

We visualise the matrix $\Delta Total_{ij}$ as a heatmap with sectors on the vertical axis and countries on the horizontal axis. This representation highlights (i) which sectors are most sensitive to the sequencing shock within each country, and (ii) how the pattern of exposure differs across countries. High absolute values $|\Delta Total_{ij}|$ identify sectors that play a central role in propagating or absorbing the shock in the national production structure.

Country-specific sectoral profiles

For selected countries (notably Morocco and Nigeria), we also plot $\Delta Total_{ij}$ as a bar chart over sectors i . These “sectoral shock profiles” show how the aggregate national impact is built up from gains and losses across individual sectors, and provide an intuitive visualization of the supply-chain channels through which the sequencing investment operates. In economies where upstream sectors such as energy, grains or heavy manufacturing exhibit large positive bars, the genomic shock is absorbed early in the supply chain and then transmitted downstream. Conversely, when service sectors dominate the response, the gains are concentrated closer to final demand.

Links with calibrated BCRs

Although the sectoral $\Delta Total_{ij}$ values are expressed in model units, they are consistent with the calibrated country-level benefits and BCRs derived in the

main analysis. The calibration factor k (obtained by anchoring Morocco's aggregate Δ_{MAR}^{model} to an external BCR of 3.29 for a 20 million USD investment) (Hayah et al., 2025) acts as a uniform monetary scaling. Multiplying $\Delta Total_{ij}$ by k would convert sector-level shocks into calibrated monetary contributions, and their sum over sectors in a given country j would exactly recover the calibrated national benefit used to compute $BCR_j^{calibrated}$. In this way, the sectoral shock decomposition and the calibrated BCRs are two views of the same underlying general-equilibrium response: one resolves the propagation of the shock along the supply chain, while the other summarizes its overall economic return on investment.

4. *Methodology for survey development, collection, analysis and bibliometric analysis:* We conducted a survey to better understand the interactions between IP, biodiversity genetic resources, DSI, and ABS practices across Africa. Quantitative data were summarized using descriptive statistics, while qualitative free-text responses were thematically reviewed and topic-modelled to identify recurring patterns and perspectives relevant to biodiversity genomics governance and IP policy across African research contexts. Similarly, bibliometric analysis was performed to determine African authors actively publishing in the field to date. (see Additional texts S2 in supplementary information for details on survey development, collection, and analysis methodology as well as bibliometric analysis).

Data availability

<Data available and under embargo>

Code availability

<Data available and under embargo>

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Competing interests

N. Shabangu is an employee of MGI

Authors contributions

S/N	Author name	Conceived original project idea	Project design and evolution	Literature review	Survey development and collection	Survey analysis	Survey interpretation	Economic model investigation	Data gathering and curation	Performed economic analysis	Validation of economic analysis results	Developed code for economic analysis	Production of manuscript diagram	Manuscript original draft	Manuscript revision	Supervision - oversight and leadership responsibilities	Journal correspondence	Manuscript review & editing
1	Bouabid Badaoui		✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓					✓
2	Nadia Carstens			✓											✓			✓
3	ThankGod Echezona Ebenezer	✓	✓		✓		✓				✓				✓	✓	✓	✓

S/N	Author name	Conceived original project idea	Project design and evolution	Literature review	Survey development and collection	Survey analysis	Survey interpretation	Economic model investigation	Data gathering and curation	Performed economic analysis	Validation of economic analysis results	Developed code for economic analysis	Production of manuscript diagram	Manuscript original draft	Manuscript revision	Supervision - oversight and leadership responsibilities	Journal correspondence	Manuscript review & editing
4	Yassine El Hajoui						✓	✓				✓			✓			✓
5	Elhadj Ezzahid							✓			✓				✓			✓
6	Samira Ghoor			✓											✓			✓
7	Fatma Zahra Guerfali		✓	✓										✓				✓
8	Ichrak Hayah			✓			✓			✓					✓			✓
9	Craig Kinnear			✓											✓			✓

S/N	Author name	Conceived original project idea	Project design and evolution	Literature review	Survey development and collection	Survey analysis	Survey interpretation	Economic model investigation	Data gathering and curation	Performed economic analysis	Validation of economic analysis results	Developed code for economic analysis	Production of manuscript diagram	Manuscript original draft	Manuscript revision	Supervision - oversight and leadership responsibilities	Journal correspondence	Manuscript review & editing
10	Sydney Mathebula			✓			✓								✓			✓
11	Anne WT Muigai			✓											✓			✓
12	Zahra Mungloo-Dilmohamud			✓											✓			✓
13	Julien Alban Nguinkal				✓													✓
14	Shabangu Ntji			✓	✓		✓								✓			✓

S/N	Author name	Conceived original project idea	Project design and evolution	Literature review	Survey development and collection	Survey analysis	Survey interpretation	Economic model investigation	Data gathering and curation	Performed economic analysis	Validation of economic analysis results	Developed code for economic analysis	Production of manuscript diagram	Manuscript original draft	Manuscript revision	Supervision - oversight and leadership responsibilities	Journal correspondence	Manuscript review & editing
15	Emmanuel Kolawole Oke			✓	✓										✓			✓
16	Taiwo Crossby Omotoriogun			✓											✓			✓
17	Julian O. Osuji			✓											✓			✓
18	Fouzia Radouani			✓											✓			✓
19	Radouane Raouf							✓	✓						✓			✓

S/N	Author name	Conceived original project idea	Project design and evolution	Literature review	Survey development and collection	Survey analysis	Survey interpretation	Economic model investigation	Data gathering and curation	Performed economic analysis	Validation of economic analysis results	Developed code for economic analysis	Production of manuscript diagram	Manuscript original draft	Manuscript revision	Supervision - oversight and leadership responsibilities	Journal correspondence	Manuscript review & editing
20	Abdoallah Sharaf					✓	✓						✓		✓			✓
21	Rae Marvin Smith			✓		✓	✓						✓					✓

Supplementary information

1. **Figure S1: Regional effects of income-based (Y-variables) under genetic sequencing-induced productivity shock**
2. **Figure S2: Regional effects of structural (Non-Y) economic variables under genetic sequencing-induced productivity shock**
3. **Figure S3: Country-level effects of income-based (Y-variables) under a genetic sequencing-induced productivity shock across eight African economies**
4. **Figure S4. Structural variable heatmap for selected African countries under genetic sequencing shock**
5. **Figure S5: Sectoral shock propagation networks across countries**
6. **Figure S6: <blank>**
7. **Figure S7: Supply-Chain Impact and Sectoral Shock Propagation**
8. **Figure S8: Survey analysis on Intellectual Property Landscape of Biodiversity Genetics Resources and Digital Sequence Information**
9. **Figure S9: Bibliometric analysis on biodiversity, agriculture, genomics, and bioinformatics collaborations**
10. **Additional texts S1: Economics of Intellectual Property, Digital Sequence Information, and Access and Benefit-Sharing landscape**
11. **Additional texts S2: Methodology for survey development, collection, analysis and bibliometric analysis**
12. **Additional texts S3: Technical Guide: Methodology for Calibrating GTAP-Based Economic Impact of Sequencing Investments**

Y Variables Heatmap Across African Regions and Scenarios

Figure S1. Regional effects of income-based (Y-variables) under genetic sequencing-induced productivity shock. This heatmap presents percentage change in income-related variables across four African regional blocs— Arab Maghreb Union (AMU), Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), East African Community (EAC), Southern African Development Community (SADC),— following the modeled introduction of agricultural genetic sequencing technologies in agriculture. The X-axis presents three intervention scenarios of increasing intensity, denoted by asterisks: * (low), ** (moderate), and *** (high). Each scenario corresponds to an escalating Total Factor Productivity (TFP) gain in agricultural sectors—5%, 10%, and 15%, respectively—combined with rising Capital Share Parameters (β) and Constant Elasticity of Substitution (CES) (σ). The Y-axis lists the income components analyzed: Household Capital Income (YHK), Household Labor Income (YHL), Disposable Household Income (YDH), Household Total Income (YH), Government Income (YG), and Rest-of-the-World total Income (YROW) (see Table 1 for definition of terms). All values are expressed as percentage deviations from a Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario assuming stable productivity, input shares, and trade flows. Color intensity reflects the magnitude of change, with darker blue indicating larger positive values (income gains), and lighter yellow tones representing stronger negative values (income losses).

Heatmap of Non-Y Variables Across African Regions and Scenarios

Figure S2. Regional effects of structural (Non-Y) economic variables under genetic sequencing-induced productivity shock. This heatmap shows percentage changes in key structural macroeconomic indicators across four African regional blocs—Arab Maghreb Union (AMU), Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), East African Community (EAC), and Southern African Development Community (SADC)—in response to the simulated adoption of genetic sequencing technologies in agriculture. The X-axis presents three intervention scenarios of increasing intensity, denoted by asterisks: * (low), ** (moderate), and *** (high). These correspond to 5%, 10%, and 15% increases in Total Factor Productivity (TFP) in agriculture, combined with rising Capital Share Parameters (β) and Constant Elasticity of Substitution (CES) (σ), reflecting technological intensification and capital-deepening. The Y-axis includes ten structural indicators tracked in the GTAP model: Household Consumption (C), Intermediate Consumption (CI), Composite Capital Demand (KDC), Composite Labour Demand (LDC), the Intermediate Consumption Price Index (PCI), Unit Cost of Production (PP), the Composite Capital Rental Rate (RC), Value Added (VA), the Composite Labor Wage Rate (WC), and Total Productions (XS) (see Table 1 for definition of terms). All values are expressed as percentage deviations from a Business-as-usual (BAU) scenario that assumes stable productivity, input shares, and trade flows. Color intensity reflects the magnitude and direction of change: darker red tones indicate larger gains, while pale yellow tones represent stronger losses.

Heatmap of Income Components by Country and Shock Intensity

Figure S3. Country-level effects of income-based (Y-variables) under a genetic sequencing-induced productivity shock across eight African economies. This heatmap captures percentage changes in core income variables for eight African countries—Algeria (DZA), South Africa (ZAF), Tunisia (TUN), Nigeria (NGA), Morocco (MAR), Kenya (KEN), Egypt (EGY), and Cameroon (CMR)—in response to simulated agricultural productivity shocks induced by genetic sequencing. The X-axis includes five income indicators: Household Capital Income (YHK), Household Labor Income (YHL), Disposable Household Income (YDH), Government Income (YG), and Rest-of-the-World total Income (YROW) (see Table 1 for definition of terms), each shown under three intervention scenarios of increasing intensity, denoted by asterisks: * (low), ** (moderate), and *** (high). The Y-axis lists individual countries. All values represent percentage deviations from a business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario, which assumes stable productivity, technology, and trade flows. Color intensity reflects the direction and magnitude of change: darker green indicates stronger income gains, while pale yellow to orange indicates income losses.

Combined Heatmap of Non-Y Variables by Sector and Country-Scenario

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Figure S4: Structural variable heatmap for selected African countries under genetic sequencing shock. This heatmap illustrates the percentage change in structural economic indicators across sectors and countries in response to the simulated productivity shock introduced by agricultural genetic sequencing. The Y-axis lists disaggregated structural variables by sector, including Intermediate Consumption (CI), Household Consumption (C), Composite Capital Demand (KDC), Composite Labour Demand (LDC), Intermediate Consumption Price Index (PCI), Unit Cost of Production (PP), Composite Capital Rental Rate (RC), Value Added (VA), the Composite Labor Wage Rate (WC), and Total Productions (XS) (see Table 1 for definition of terms). The X-axis shows each of the eight modeled countries—Cameroon (CMR), Egypt (EGY), Kenya (KEN), Morocco (MAR), Nigeria (NGA), South Africa (ZAF), Tunisia (TUN), and Algeria (DZA)—under three intervention scenarios of increasing intensity, denoted by asterisks: * (low), ** (moderate), and *** (high). All values represent percentage deviations from a Business-as-usual (BAU) scenario with stable productivity, input shares, and trade flows. Green tones indicate sectoral gains, while red tones reflect declines, highlighting highly heterogeneous sectoral responses to the shock across countries and intensities.

Sectoral shock propagation networks (inter-sector co-movement across QP blocks)

Figure S5: Sectoral shock propagation networks across countries. This figure shows inter-sectoral co-movement networks constructed from GTAP shock responses across the five QP blocks (XS, CI, C, LDC, KDC). For each country (A–H), nodes represent GTAP sectors (English labels), with node size proportional to the sector’s total absolute contribution aggregated across QP blocks. Edges connect sector pairs with the strongest co-movement (absolute correlation across QP block responses), highlighting how the sequencing-induced shock propagates through production, intermediate demand, final demand, and factor-use channels. The resulting network “shape” provides an interpretable fingerprint of each country’s structural transmission mechanism, revealing sectoral hubs and tightly coupled clusters that dominate the economy-wide adjustment to the sequencing shock.

Figure S6: <blank>

A

Sectoral shock impact across countries
(aggregated over XS, CI, C, LDC and KDC)

B

Morocco - sectoral contribution to the GTAP shock

C

Nigeria - sectoral contribution to the GTAP shock

D

Country Share of Total Calibrated Benefits

Figure S7: Supply-Chain Impact and Sectoral Shock Propagation. **A:** Sector–country heatmap of aggregated shock ($\Delta\text{Total}_{\{ij\}}$) across XS, CI, C, LDC and KDC. **B:** Morocco – sectoral contribution to the GTAP shock ($\Delta\text{Total}_{\{ij\}}$ for MAR). **C:** Nigeria – sectoral contribution to the GTAP shock ($\Delta\text{Total}_{\{ij\}}$ for NGA). **D:** Country share of total calibrated benefits from the sequencing investment.

**This section is on Survey Analysis on Intellectual Property (IP)
Landscape of Biodiversity Genetics Resources and Digital
Sequence Information (The next 10 figures are Figure S8.1 - S8.9
respectively)**

Figure S8.1. Survey-based overview of the IP landscape for biodiversity genetics resources and Digital Sequence Information (DSI) in Africa. (a-f) General survey participant demographics, including gender, age group, country of origin, country of residence, institutional affiliation, and country of institutional affiliation. **(g-h)** Most participants reported active engagement and relevant expertise, with 84.3% currently involved in genome or genome-related projects and 88.3% indicating at least a basic level of knowledge of biodiversity genetics resources and DSI. **(i)** A minority of participants (22.5%) preferred unrestricted access, use, and reuse of their research data related to biodiversity genetics resources and DSI. **(k)** Sentiment analysis of 91 responses indicates that plant biotechnology and plant breeding represent the primary research areas of the participants. **(l)** Sentiment analysis of 74 responses shows strong agreement that limited access to resources is the most prominent barrier in the field of biodiversity, genetic resources, and DSI. **(m)** Sentiment analysis of 65 responses indicates strong participant knowledge of national and regional IP laws in Africa, whereas **(n)** sentiment analysis of 53 responses suggests a moderate level of knowledge of international IP laws. **(o)** Sentiment analysis of 34 responses reveals generally positive perceptions regarding the ability of IP frameworks to protect, share, and commercialize research outputs. Statistical and sentiment analyses were conducted using Python (Pandas for data analysis), NLTK for sentiment analysis, and BERTopic for topic modeling, with visualizations generated using Matplotlib and Seaborn.

(a) Participant's access to latest equipment and technological infrastructure required for biodiversity genetics resources or Digital Sequence Information (DSI)

(b) Participant's technical skills needs to operate new technologies, equipment, and tools required for genetic resources or DSI

(c) Participant's access to technical skills to use new tools or operate new technologies and equipment related to genetics resources or DSI

(d) Participant's awareness of any national policy on technology transfer in his country

(e) Role of Intellectual Property (IP) rights in facilitating or hindering participant's access to the technology and equipment required for your work on genetics resources or DSI (n = 31)

(f) Access obtaining to latest equipment and technological infrastructure required for participant's work on biodiversity genetics resources or Digital Sequence Information (DSI) (n = 45)

Figure S8.2. Survey-based overview of the IP landscape for biodiversity genetics resources and Digital Sequence Information (DSI) in Africa. (a) A majority of survey participants (76.5%) reported access to the latest equipment and technological infrastructure required for work on biodiversity genetics resources or DSI. **(b)** Most participants (90.2%) indicated that they possess the technical skills needed to operate new technologies, equipment, and tools required for genetic resources or DSI. **(c)** A majority of participants (68.6%) reported access to technical support or training enabling the use of new tools and technologies related to genetic resources or DSI. **(d)** Approximately half of the participants (51%) reported awareness of national policies on technology transfer in their respective countries. **(e)** Sentiment analysis of 31 responses suggests agreement that IP rights could facilitate access to required technologies and equipment through resource access rights. **(f)** Sentiment analysis of 45 responses indicates that limited access to sequencing infrastructure represents the most significant gap in the availability of advanced equipment and technological infrastructure for work on biodiversity genetics resources and DSI. Statistical and sentiment analyses were conducted using Python (Pandas for data analysis), NLTK for sentiment analysis, and BERTopic for topic modeling, with visualizations generated using Matplotlib and Seaborn.

(a) Participant's Does Participant's country have a national Intellectual Property (IP) Office

(b) Participant's awareness of the IP processes in your country

(c) Does participant's have an IP Office / Technology Transfer Office in institution or organisation

(d) Participant's interesting in commercializing research or innovations from genetic resources or DSI

(e) Which approach would participant's follow to commercialize research

(f) Is participant's believe that increased awareness of IP will lead to increased sharing of genetic resources or DSI data across Africa

Figure S8.3. Survey-based overview of the IP landscape for biodiversity genetics resources and Digital Sequence Information (DSI) in Africa. (a) A majority of survey participants (62.7%) reported that their country has a national IP office, while **(b)** approximately half of the participants (53.9%) reported being aware of IP processes in their country. **(c)** Only 38.2% of participants indicated that their institution has an IP office or a technology transfer office. **(d)** A majority of participants (86.3%) expressed interest in commercializing research outputs or innovations derived from genetic resources or DSI. **(e)** About one-third of participants (34.1%) identified patent licensing as a preferred approach for commercialization. **(f)** Finally, most participants (80.4%) believed that increasing awareness of IP would promote greater sharing of genetic resources and DSI data across Africa. Statistical analyses were conducted using Python (Pandas for data analysis), with visualizations generated using Matplotlib and Seaborn.

(a) Does participant's apply for patent rights for work on genetic resources or Digital Sequence Information (DSI)

(b) Have Participant's ever applied for or obtained a patent within country or region in Africa

(c) Have Participant's ever applied for or obtained a patent outside country or region in Africa

(d) Participant's have any patents that are yet to expire

(e) Any direct economic or financial benefit from patenting participant's research outputs

(f) Does benefit return back into participant's research, research group, organisation, or country

(g) Participant's believe that an increase in patenting practices by African researchers and organisations will lead to increased sharing of genetic resources or DSI across Africa

(h) Participant's think patent applicants should required to disclose the origin of any genetic resources or DSI that are used in the development of inventions

Figure S8.4. Survey-based overview of the IP landscape for biodiversity genetics resources and Digital Sequence Information (DSI) in Africa. (a) A majority of survey participants (72.5%) reported not applying for patent rights for their work on genetic resources or DSI. Consistently, (b) most participants (91.2%) reported never having applied for or obtained a patent within their country or region in Africa. Similarly, (c) a majority of participants (88.2%) reported never having applied for or obtained a patent outside their country or region in Africa. (d) Most participants (92.2%) reported not holding any active (unexpired) patents. (e) Slightly more than half of participants (56.9%) reported receiving direct economic or financial benefits from patenting research outputs, while (f) nearly half (48.0%) indicated that such benefits are reinvested into their research, research group, institution, or country. (g) A majority of participants (70.6%) believed that increased patenting activity by African researchers and organizations would promote greater sharing of genetic resources or DSI across Africa, and (h) most participants (81.4%) agreed that patent applicants should be required to disclose the origin of any genetic resources or DSI used in the development of their inventions. Statistical analyses were conducted using Python (Pandas for data analysis), with visualizations generated using Matplotlib and Seaborn.

(a) Does participant's country have an effective system for the protection of copyright

(b) Participant's have a copyright strategy for scientific research and outputs

(c) Participant's understanding the benefits of copyrights protection for scientific research and outputs?

(d) Role of copyright law in participant's work (n = 43)

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Figure S8.5. Survey-based overview of the IP landscape for biodiversity genetics resources and Digital Sequence Information (DSI) in Africa. (a) Nearly half of survey participants (52.9%) reported that their country has an effective system for the protection of copyright. **(b)** Slightly more than half of participants (58.8%) indicated that they do not have a specific copyright strategy for their scientific research and outputs to prevent unauthorized copying or reproduction of their work. **(c)** A majority of participants (65.7%) reported understanding the benefits of copyright protection for their scientific research and outputs. **(d)** Sentiment analysis of 43 responses suggests generally positive perceptions of the role of copyright law in protecting scientific publications from unauthorized copying or reproduction. Statistical and sentiment analyses were conducted using Python (Pandas for data analysis), NLTK for sentiment analysis, and BERTopic for topic modeling, with visualizations generated using Matplotlib and Seaborn.

(a) Does participant's trademark work which are related to biodiversity genetics resources or DSI

(b) Participant's currently have any trademark relating to biodiversity genetics resources or DSI

(c) Participant's believe that an increase in trademarks practices by African researchers and organisations will lead to increased sharing of genetic resources or DSI across Africa

Figure S8.6. Survey-based overview of the IP landscape for biodiversity genetics resources and Digital Sequence Information (DSI) in Africa. (a) Nearly half of survey participants (45.1%) reported that they do not trademark work related to biodiversity genetics resources or DSI. **(b)** More than half of participants (61.8%) indicated that they do not currently hold any trademarks associated with biodiversity genetics resources or DSI. **(c)** Nearly half of participants (51.0%) believed that increased trademarking practices by African researchers and organizations would promote greater sharing of genetic resources or DSI across Africa. Statistical analysis was conducted using Python (Pandas for data analysis), with visualizations generated using Matplotlib and Seaborn.

(a) Participant's considering trade secrets to be a valuable means of protecting the results of work on genetic resources or DSI

(b) Participant's currently have any trade secrets relating to genetic resources or DSI

(c) Considering Geographical indications (GIs) to be a valuable means of protecting the results of participant's work

(d) Considering Plant Variety Rights to be a valuable means of protecting the results of participant's work

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Figure S8.7. Survey-based overview of the IP landscape for biodiversity genetics resources and Digital Sequence Information (DSI) in Africa. (a) More than half of survey participants (62.7%) considered trade secrets to be a valuable means of protecting the results of their work on genetic resources or DSI. **(b)** A majority of participants (86.3%) reported currently holding trade secrets related to genetic resources or DSI. **(c)** Most participants (78.4%) considered geographical indications (GIs) to be a valuable means of protecting the results of their work, while **(d)** nearly half of participants (47.5%) considered plant variety rights to be a valuable means of protecting the results of their work. Statistical analysis was conducted using Python (Pandas for data analysis), with visualizations generated using Matplotlib and Seaborn.

(a) Participant's share DSI on unrestricted open access platforms

(b) Participant's thinks less resourced institutions and countries can benefit greatly from DSI

(c) Participant's thinks it would be beneficial to secure DSI via Intellectual Property (IP) rights

(d) Participant's consider IP as an incentive to encourage unrestricted data sharing

(e) Participant's benefit or institution obtained from unrestricted open access platforms (n = 41)

(f) Participant's major concern with unrestricted sharing and reuse of genetic resources or DSI (n = 22)

(g) Participant's consider IP to be an incentive to encourage unrestricted data sharing (n = 16)

Figure S8.8. Survey-based overview of the IP landscape for biodiversity genetics resources and Digital Sequence Information (DSI) in Africa. (a) Slightly more than half of survey participants (52.9%) reported sharing DSI through unrestricted open-access platforms. **(b)** A majority of participants (64.7%) believed that less-resourced institutions and countries can benefit substantially from access to DSI. **(c)** More than half of participants (67.6%) considered securing DSI through intellectual property (IP) rights to be beneficial. **(d)** Nearly half of participants (42.2%) were uncertain whether IP could serve as an incentive to encourage unrestricted data sharing. **(e)** Sentiment analysis of 41 responses suggests generally positive perceptions of benefits obtained from unrestricted open-access platforms by participants or their institutions. **(f)** Sentiment analysis of 22 responses indicates that lack of acknowledgment of their work represents the primary concern associated with unrestricted sharing and reuse of genetic resources or DSI. **(g)** Sentiment analysis of 16 responses reveals that participants would consider IP as an incentive to encourage unrestricted data sharing only in cases where IP sharing rights are ensured. Statistical and sentiment analyses were conducted using Python (Pandas for data analysis), NLTK for sentiment analysis, and BERTopic for topic modeling, with visualizations generated using Matplotlib and Seaborn.

(a) Existing Intellectual Property (IP) related challenges to commercializing participant's research on genetic resources or Digital Sequence Information (DSI) (n = 37)

(b) Participant's consider as the impact of IP rights for genetic resources or DSI for biodiversity and agricultural genomics in Africa (n = 27)

(c) How can biodiversity genomics discipline and the African BioGenome Project influence IPs across Africa and vice versa (n = 44)

(c) What are the challenges that impede the economic or financial benefits of IP rights from returning to participant, organisation, or country (n = 28)

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Figure S8.9. Survey-based overview of the IP landscape for biodiversity genetics resources and Digital Sequence Information (DSI) in Africa. (a) Sentiment analysis of 37 responses suggests that participants are generally unaware of existing intellectual property (IP), related challenges to commercializing research on genetic resources or Digital Sequence Information (DSI). (b) Sentiment analysis of 27 responses indicates that maximizing benefits is perceived as the primary impact of IP rights for genetic resources or DSI in biodiversity and agricultural genomics in Africa. (c) Sentiment analysis of 44 responses suggests that promoting equitable benefit-sharing is viewed as a key mechanism through which the biodiversity genomics community and the African BioGenome Project could influence IP frameworks across Africa, and vice versa. (d) Sentiment analysis of 28 responses indicates that limited economic resources represent a major challenge impeding the return of economic or financial benefits from IP rights to participants, their institutions, or their countries. Sentiment analysis was conducted using Python (Pandas for data analysis), NLTK for sentiment analysis, and BERTopic for topic modeling, with visualizations generated using Matplotlib and Seaborn.

This section is on bibliometric analysis

Figure S9A: Topic emphasis and collaborations for African affiliated authors working towards genomics and bioinformatics (bibliometric analysis). A network diagram showing the largest emphasis in topics highlighted in works towards agricultural and biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics. Where the size of the nodes show the emphasis of these topics in the abstracts and edges represent the interconnectivity between topics. This figure was generated using R v 4.4.1 using the package Bibliometrix v. 5.1.1 (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017).

Figure S9B: Topic emphasis and collaborations for African affiliated authors working towards genomics and bioinformatics (bibliometric analysis). A network diagram overlaid onto a map, showing collaboration between international authors with African researchers. This figure was generated using R v 4.4.1 using the package Bibliometrix v. 5.1.1 (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017).

Additional texts S1:

Economics of Intellectual Property, Digital Sequence Information, and Access and Benefit-Sharing landscape

Genetic Resources and International Intellectual Property Law

The legal framework for the global governance of genetic resources can be found in various international treaties adopted by different international organisations. The preeminent international treaty in this regard is the Convention on Biological Diversity of 1992 (CBD) and the Nagoya Protocol to the CBD. Other relevant international legal instruments in this regard include the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture, the Agreement on the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Marine Biodiversity of Areas beyond National Jurisdiction, and the WIPO Treaty on Intellectual Property, Genetic Resources and Associated Traditional Knowledge. The CBD is aimed at the conservation of biological diversity, the sustainable use of its components and the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of the utilization of genetic resources. The objective of the Nagoya Protocol is the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources, including by appropriate access to genetic resources and by appropriate transfer of relevant technologies. The CBD and the Nagoya Protocol therefore both provide for an access-and-benefit-sharing (ABS) system for genetic resources.

In order to facilitate compliance, the Nagoya Protocol mandates parties to the Protocol to implement measures to monitor and improve transparency concerning the utilization of genetic resources. According to Article 17 of the Nagoya Protocol, these measures include the use of designated checkpoints to “collect or receive, as appropriate, relevant information related to prior informed consent, to the source of the genetic resource, to the establishment of mutually agreed terms, and/or to the utilization of genetic resources, as appropriate.” This requirement of having designated checkpoints to monitor the use of genetic resources has fuelled demands by developing countries, including African countries, for the inclusion of disclosure of origin requirements in international intellectual property law. Specifically, as it relates to patent applications, by requiring patent applicants to disclose the source of any genetic resources used in their claimed inventions, state parties can convert national patent offices into designated checkpoints for identifying inventions based on genetic resources.

In May 2024, WIPO Member States adopted the WIPO Treaty on Intellectual Property, Genetic Resources and Associated Traditional Knowledge (WIPO, 2024b). Article 3 of this WIPO Treaty mandates parties to implement a disclosure of origin requirement (or source) in their national patent systems. Where the claimed invention in a patent application is based on genetic resources, Article 3.1 of the Treaty mandates parties to require patent applicants to disclose the country of origin of the genetic resources or, where this is not known to the applicant, the source of

the genetic resources. One of the key strengths of this WIPO Treaty is that its implementation can provide a means for states to monitor the use and commercialization of genetic resources. Unlike the KMGBF, a key limitation of the Treaty is its failure to explicitly address the issue of digital sequence information (DSI) on genetic resources. This does not however prevent parties to the Treaty from addressing the issue of DSI at the national level. As at the time of writing, this WIPO Treaty is not yet in force as it has only been ratified by two African states i.e. Malawi and Uganda (WIPO, 2025). The Treaty will enter into force after it has been ratified by 15 states (WIPO, 2024a).

Genetic Resources, Intellectual Property, and Survey on Data and Benefit-Sharing

Intellectual property law functions as a core mechanism through which societies regulate the ownership, circulation and economic valorisation of knowledge and innovation. According to the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), intellectual property refers to the creations of the mind, including inventions, literary and artistic works, symbols, names, images, and designs used in commerce (WIPO, 2023). IP is conventionally divided into two principal categories, industrial property, which includes patents, trademarks, industrial designs, and geographical indicators, and copyright and related rights, which protects literary, artistic, and scientific works, including performances and broadcasts.

While copyright protection arises automatically upon creation, enforcement remains uneven across jurisdictions, particularly in the digital environment where near perfect copies can be reproduced and disseminated at minimal cost (Lessig, 2004). These challenges are amplified in low- and middle-income regions, where institutional capacity, legal infrastructure and access to remedies are often constrained. As a result, IP systems though formally universal operate asymmetrically in practice, privileging actors with greater technological, legal and financial resources.

The protection of intellectual property has deep historical roots within European legal traditions. Patents for inventions were granted in Venice as early as the fifteenth century, but modern international IP governance emerged in the late nineteenth century with the adoption of the Paris Convention for the protection of Industrial property (1883) and the Berne Convention for the protection of literary and Artistic works (1886). These were followed by the Madrid Agreement (1891) on trademarks and the Hague Agreement (1925) on industrial designs.

These treaties were designed to harmonise national IP laws and facilitate cross border protection for rights holders, primarily within industrialised economies. Over time the International IP system expanded to include more than 25 treaties administered by WIPO, and IP rights were further recognised as human rights under Article 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. However, the evolution of IP

law reflects the economic and political priorities of dominant states rather than a neutral or universally equitable framework (Drahos, 2002; Sell, 2003).

The African IP landscape is inseparable from its colonial history. During the “Scramble for Africa” formalised at the Berlin West Africa Conference (1884-1885), European powers simultaneously consolidated territorial control and extended their legal and economic systems across the continent. IP treaties functioned as instruments for protecting European industrial and cultural interest in colonial markets rather than fostering endogenous innovation in Africa (Shillington, 1989, Mazrui & Wondji, 2000).

Between 1885 and 1935, international IP treaties were selectively extended to African territories through colonial administration. By 1935, only Morocco, South Africa, and Tunisia had ratified international IP agreements, largely through representation by colonial powers rather than autonomous participation (Ncube, 2017). These early efforts at establishing international IP law are viewed as forms of legal neo-colonialism, embedding asymmetrical power relations into global IP system (Rahmatian, 2009 ; Peukert, 2012)

Post independence, African states entered the international IP system under significant structural constraints. Although treaty membership expanded rapidly after the 1960s, participation in rule making remained limited. By 1965, approximately half of African states had joined the Paris and Berne Conventions, but the average number of treaties ratified per country remained low, and implementation varied widely (Kongolo, 2014).

The governance of genetic resources occupies a complex intersection between IP law, environmental law, and development policy. The adoption of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) in 1992 marked a paradigm shift by recognising state sovereignty over genetic resources and introducing the principle of fair and equitable benefit sharing. This was later operationalised through the Nagoya Protocol and Access and benefit sharing (2010).

However, IP regimes, particularly patent systems governed by the TRIPS Agreement often operate independently of biodiversity governance frameworks. This fragmentation has enabled situations in which genetic resources originating from biodiversity rich regions are patented and commercialised elsewhere without meaningful benefit sharing, a process widely described as biopiracy (Mgbeoji, 2007; Dutfield, 2010).

The challenge has become more acute with the rise of digital sequence information (DSI). Because DSI can be accessed, stored, and analysed without physical transfer of biological material, it frequently falls outside existing ABS mechanisms. The regulatory gap of DSI undermines the objectives of the CBD and disproportionately disadvantages regions such as Africa, which harbours significant biodiversity but

lacks equivalent bioinformatics infrastructure (Laird et al., 2020; Rabone et al., 2019).

Africa's position within the global IP landscape remains structurally constrained despite widespread treaty adoption. While international norms are largely shaped by TRIPS and WIPO administered agreements, African countries vary significantly in their participation in supplementary treaties and domestic implementation and enforcement. This heterogeneity creates fragmented legal environments that complicate regional collaboration and weaken negotiating powers in international forums (Maskus, 2012).

The establishment of WIPO as a United Nations agency in 1974 marked a rhetorical shift towards development-oriented IP governance. Nevertheless, critics argue that substantive policy outcomes continue to favour technologically advanced economies, reinforcing global innovation hierarchies (Sell, 2003; Drahos & Braithwaite, 2004).

New opportunities can arise with the development of Intellectual property protocol under the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA), which represents an important opportunity to reconfigure regional IP governance. If implemented effectively, it could harmonise trade related IP rules while preserving policy space for protecting traditional knowledge, biodiversity and public interest innovation.

Artificial intelligence is transforming the creation, analysis and commercial exploitation of knowledge across sectors including healthcare, agriculture, and biodiversity research. AI systems trained on large genomic datasets raise unresolved questions concerning inventorship, authorship, ownership and beneficiation (Contreras, 2021). Existing IP doctrines were not designed to accommodate non-human creativity or algorithmic innovation, and current legal responses remain fragmented.

For Africa, the convergence of AI and DSI presents both opportunity and risk. Without deliberate regulatory reform, AI-driven innovation may exacerbate existing inequities by enabling the extraction and valorisation of African genetic data without corresponding benefits to source countries or communities. This highlights the urgency of integrating IP reform with digital governance and biodiversity policy.

Several persistent loopholes characterise the current IP landscape. First, TRIPS driven harmonisation limits national policy flexibility, constraining the ability of African states to tailor IP laws to local innovation systems. DSI remains weakly regulated, enabling the circumvention of benefit-sharing obligations. Enforcement mechanisms continue to privilege well-resourced rights holders, marginalising public research institutions and indigenous knowledge holders.

Despite the challenges, Africa retains significant scope for IP policy Innovation. There is a need for an Africa- focused approach that is grounded in regional

cooperation, biodiversity stewardship and inclusive innovation, offering a pathway towards aligning IP governance with sustainable development goals. The reform can be supported with empirical evidence of systemic analysis of treaty membership, domestic legislation and innovation outcomes.

This study provides one of the first survey-based empirical overviews of the Intellectual property (IP) landscapes for biodiversity genetic resources and digital sequence information (DSI) in Africa, revealing a complex interplay between scientific capacity, access to infrastructure, IP awareness and benefit sharing. While African researchers demonstrate high levels of engagement in genomics and biodiversity-related research, the results underscore persistent structural and governance gaps that limit equitable access, protection and benefit realization from genetic resources and DSI.

There appears to be a significant scientific engagement with less commensurate IP utilization (Figure 10A). A high proportion of participants are actively involved in genomics research (Figure S8.1), with previous reports highlighting Africa's growing role in biodiversity genomics and agricultural biotechnology (African Union, 2015, Hendre et al., 2019). However, this engagement is not matched by effective IP utilization (Figure S8.4). The findings that over 90% of respondents have never applied for patents either within or outside Africa (Figure S8.4), reflects long standing concern that IP systems on the continent remain underutilized by public-sector researchers due to limited institutional support, costs and perceived misalignment with academic incentives (Munyi & De Jonge, 2015, Chiarolla et al., 2019).

The reliance on trade secrets, reported by a large majority of the respondents (Figure S8.7), further suggests a preference for informal or defensive protection strategies over formal IP rights. While trade secrets may offer short-term control, they limit transparency, collaboration, and scalable benefit-sharing, particularly in publicly funded research contexts (Oldham, 2014). This pattern indicates that African researchers may be protecting knowledge in ways that unintentionally constrain broader innovation and regional cooperation.

Although a majority of participants reported access to modern equipment and technical support (Figure S8.2), limited access to sequencing infrastructure emerged as the most significant technological gap. This finding corroborates with existing literature that describes Africa as “data-rich but infrastructure poor” in genomics, where data generation increasingly depends on collaboration with external institutions (Bezuidenhout et al., 2017). Such asymmetries raise concerns about who ultimately controls downstream applications, commercialization, and IP derived from African genetic resources and DSI.

The survey further reveals that access to DSI through open platforms is widely perceived as beneficial (Figure S8.8), particularly for less-resourced institutions. However, uncertainty regarding IP as an incentive for unrestricted data sharing

reflects global tensions in DSI governance (Figure S8.8), especially the ongoing discourse under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and its Nagoya Protocol on DSI (UNEP Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022, Switzer et al., 2025).

The respondents reported the existence of national IP offices and copyrights systems (Figure S8.5); fewer than half were aware of institutional IP or technology transfer offices (Figure S8.3 and S8.9). This gap between formal legal structures and functional implementation echoes broader critiques that African IP regimes are often limited in operational capacity, enforcement mechanism and integration with biodiversity governance frameworks (Maskus & Reichman, 2005, Deere, 2008)

Notably, strong participant support for disclosure of origin requirements (Figure S8.4) suggests alignment with calls for greater transparency in patent systems to prevent biopiracy and ensure equitable benefit sharing (Chiarolla & Jungcurt, 2011). However, the uneven adoption of such requirements across African jurisdictions weakens their collective effectiveness, particularly in the context of cross-border research and commercialization.

Despite widespread interest in commercializing research outputs, actual economic returns from IP remain limited and uneven. Where benefits are realized, they are often reinvested into research rather than generating sustained institutional or national gains. This supports existing evidence that, without robust innovation ecosystems and access to capital, IP rights alone are insufficient to translate biodiversity research into meaningful socioeconomic benefits (Lema et al., 2018).

The perception that increased patenting and IP awareness could promote greater data sharing is particularly noteworthy, as it challenges the assumption that IP necessarily restricts openness. Instead, it suggests that African researchers may view IP as a mechanism for secure sharing, provided attribution, recognition and benefit sharing safeguards are in place.

The African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) presents a strategic opportunity to address fragmentation in IP governance related to genetic resources and DSI. The survey findings support arguments for developing continent-wide principles or minimum standards, particularly on disclosure of origin, benefit sharing, and technology access, while retaining national and regional implementation (African Union, 2018). Such an approach could strengthen Africa's negotiating position in global DSI discussions and reduce regulatory arbitrage.

However, harmonization alone will not guarantee equitable outcomes. Without targeted investment in infrastructure, institutional IP capacity, and awareness of international IP frameworks, benefits may accrue disproportionately to already well-resourced institutions, exacerbating existing inequalities.

Further interpretation on survey on genetic resources, DSI, Intellectual Property, and Access and Benefit-Sharing

This statement means that, according to the survey results, the behavior of African researchers in sharing Digital Sequence Information (DSI) does not depend on their level of knowledge about intellectual property laws.

Initially, the research hypothesis assumed that African researchers who were less aware of Intellectual Property (IP) legal frameworks would be more reluctant to deposit their sequence data in public databases. This was due to fears of uncontrolled appropriation, loss of rights, or non compliance with benefit sharing.

However, the statistical analysis (Figure 10A and 10B) shows that this hypothesis is not confirmed empirically. The non-significant result ($p = 0.16$) (Figure 10B) indicates that the relationship between the level of IP awareness and the willingness to share DSI is not statistically demonstrable. In other words, one cannot conclude that better knowledge of IP rules makes researchers more or less inclined to share data.

This is perfectly illustrated by the violin plot (Figure 10B), which compares the distribution of cumulative knowledge scores of intellectual property laws between researchers who shared their data and those who did not. The two distributions overlap widely, indicating the absence of a clear or systematic difference between the two groups. In fact, among researchers who shared their data, knowledge levels are very heterogeneous (Figure 10A and S8). Some are very informed, others are not (Figure S8.1 - S8.5), and a similar variability is observed among those who did not share their data. The average or median scores do not show a significant gap between the groups, which is consistent with the reported non-significant statistical result ($p = 0.16$).

This finding is clearly demonstrated by the Sankey flow diagram; it traces the pathways of African researchers through several decision making stages, from institutional affiliation and project type to awareness of DSI, intellectual property processes, national policies, and finally to the ultimate choices of sharing or commercializing (Figure 10A). The diagram shows that many flow paths lead to the “Share (IP) = Yes” option. This includes paths from researchers reporting a low level of knowledge or a lack of familiarity with DSI. The decision trajectories appear non linear and very diverse. This suggests that the choice to share does not depend strongly on the initial level of knowledge of IP frameworks. Furthermore, the diagram (Figure 10A) highlights the influence of other determining factors, such as national policies, access preferences, industry collaborations, or the academic environment. Overall, the figure (Figure 10) indicates that DSI sharing is a complex process. It is shaped by institutional, policy, and collaborative determinants, rather than by knowledge of intellectual property laws alone. This confirms that the willingness to

share persists despite information gaps, under the effect of scientific, ethical, and collaborative motivations.

Bibliometric analysis

To situate this analysis within the wider research landscape, we examined thematic emphasis and international collaboration patterns in genomics and bioinformatics. Figure S9A indicates that genetics serves as a central research domain, with frequent connections to agriculture, biodiversity conservation and computer science, reflecting the applied orientation of this work toward food systems, environmental management and data-intensive methods. Figure S9B illustrates the collaborative dimension of this research, showing dense and sustained co-authorship links between African researchers and partners in Europe, North America and Asia. The resulting scheme is one of a research field that is simultaneously grounded in local priorities and embedded within global scientific networks.

Additional texts S2

Methodology for survey development, collection, analysis and bibliometric analysis

1. *Survey development and collection:* We conducted a cross-sectional survey using a structured, self-administered questionnaire to document practices, perceptions, and governance challenges related to biodiversity genetic resources, digital sequence information (DSI), and intellectual property (IP) across Africa. A questionnaire was disseminated through targeted outreach to stakeholders and institutions actively engaged in genomics, biodiversity research, bioinformatics, conservation science, and the generation or use of DSI. Eligible participants included researchers, laboratory scientists, bioinformaticians, policy actors, and institutional representatives working within academic, public, and research organizations. Respondents were invited to complete a standardized electronic form. The questionnaire comprised eight thematic sections covering demographic characteristics, research domains and organismal focus, access to technology and infrastructure, awareness of national and institutional IP frameworks, patenting and other IP practices, access and benefit-sharing considerations, and governance-related challenges. Both closed-ended questions, including binary and multiple-choice items, and open-ended questions were used to capture quantitative indicators and qualitative contextual insights. Responses were collected electronically and curated for completeness and internal consistency.
2. *Survey analysis (Figure S8):* Survey data were analysed using custom Python script to generate descriptive statistics for quantitative data, visual summaries, and qualitative insights (free-text responses) into the IP landscape of biodiversity genetics resources and DSI across Africa. Quantitative survey responses were processed using pandas library for data handling and cleaning (McKinney, 2010), including normalization of categorical responses, removal of missing or invalid entries, and case-insensitive grouping to ensure consistency. Frequency distributions were visualized as donut plots using matplotlib (Hunter, 2007) and seaborn (Waskom, 2021), applying color-blind-friendly palettes. Percentages were calculated relative to the total number of valid responses per survey item. Free-text survey responses were analysed using an integrated topic modeling and sentiment analysis workflow. Topic modeling was performed using BERTopic (Grootendorst, 2022), which combines sentence embeddings generated with SentenceTransformer models (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019), dimensionality reduction via UMAP (McInnes et al., 2020), and density-based clustering using HDBSCAN (Campello et al.,

2013). Low-information responses and non-informative topics were filtered automatically and manually to improve interpretability. Sentiment polarity was quantified using the VADER sentiment analyzer implemented in NLTK (Hutto & Gilbert, 2014). Topic distributions and sentiment-volume visualizations were used to summarize key themes, perceptions, and challenges related to IP, data sharing, and benefit-sharing in biodiversity genomics across Africa.

3. *Survey analysis (Alluvial plot and violin plot, Figure 10)*: Insights into the survey was produced through the respondents' answers in relation to their current and future contributions towards: Generating digital sequence information, their intentions towards generating IP and commercialising these generated resources (see paragraph below on justifications for using specific survey questions). For this we made use of select categorical questions, which was then stratified by their affiliations to an organisation or institutions operating in countries that are member states of the African Union. Responses from seventeen questions were incorporated into the final alluvial plot that was generated through R v 4.4.1 using the package ggaluvial v 0.21.5 (Brunson & Read, 2023). We further interrogated the questions to determine how knowledge related questions influence a respondent's willingness to share DSI on public repositories. To achieve this, we scored nine knowledge-based questions with a value of either 0 or 1 for where respondents declare knowledge. An exception was to their self-reported knowledge which had four categories ranging from "not knowledgeable" to "very knowledgeable", which was scored 0 to 3 respectively. All Knowledge-based questions related to Technical knowledge, IP policy, IP support, Trademarking, Incentives for sharing DSI. The maximum score for these questions was 11. The number of respondents that declared that DSI sharing doesn't apply to their research were 29, these were not included in this analysis. Once this data was omitted, we checked that that data was normally distributed before then generating a violin plot displaying cumulative scores received by respondents that either shared their DSI or did not share it to the public. Finally, a t-test was performed in R to determine significance.

The survey questions in Figure 10 shows information flow using a subset of the survey questions from Figure S8. Questions for Figure 10 were selected based on a) relevance for statistical segmentation, b) analyzing the impact of gender, governance, and institutions, c) economically important to identify who is actually participating in the genomics economy and the associated value chains, d) contains information on the capacity to transform biodiversity into economic value, to invest in the bioeconomy, and to generate innovation (Barro, 1990; Lucas, 1988), e) central to the economic analysis by assessing how IP influences incentives to invest, to commercialize, and to generate value from genetic resources and DSI (Romer, 1990), and f) measure the

economic impact of data sharing and IP mechanisms on the development of the African bioeconomy.

4. *Bibliometric analysis (Figure S9A and S9B)*: Bibliometric analysis was performed to determine African authors actively publishing in the field to date. For this we initially defined our search parameters. We queried the OpenAlex (<https://openalex.org/>) database which contains 279 million data points (Accessed 22 October 2025). Briefly, the search criteria was limited to works that refer to genomics, bioinformatics, patents and intellectual property relating to biodiversity and agriculture. We selected a range of combinations to capture all relevant datapoints. We further limited the search to contributions by authors with African-based affiliations irrespective of international collaboration. Since OpenAlex generates dynamic query results with columns that only have data present, we initially had to account for missing columns before concatenating the separate datasets in R v 4.4.1. Following this all duplicate entries were removed and the resulting dataset was visualised using Biblioshiny, implemented in Biblometrix V 5.1.1 (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017).

Additional texts S3

Technical Guide: Methodology for Calibrating GTAP-Based Economic Impact of Sequencing Investments

Technical Guide: Methodology for Calibrating GTAP-Based Economic Impact of Sequencing Investments

1.0 Introduction to the Analytical Framework

This technical guide provides a transparent, step-by-step methodology for economists and data analysts seeking to understand and replicate the process of translating relative economic impacts from a Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) model into absolute, policy-relevant metrics like economic benefits and Benefit-Cost Ratios (BCRs). The central analytical challenge is that CGE models produce dimensionless, relative impacts. This process solves that challenge by hinging on a crucial calibration step that anchors the model's outputs against an external, real-world economic benchmark. To begin, it is essential to first understand the foundational data and standardized notation used throughout the analysis.

2.0 Foundational Elements: GTAP Data and Standardized Notation

Establishing a clear and consistent foundation is a strategic prerequisite for any robust economic analysis. This section defines the core data source, the specific units of measurement, and the mathematical notation that underpins the entire analytical workflow. This precision ensures clarity in all subsequent calculations and interpretations.

2.1 The GTAP Database and Monetary Units

The analysis is conducted using results derived from a computable general equilibrium (CGE) model calibrated on the **GTAP 11 Data Base**. Within this standard framework, all monetary values are expressed in millions of current U.S. dollars.

For analytical convenience, an intermediate preprocessing step was performed where these monetary flows were scaled down by a factor of 10^4 . Consequently, all initial monetary differences (Δ) derived from the model are expressed in "model units," which are directly proportional to (million USD / 10^4). This scaling is a matter

of analytical convenience and has no bearing on the final results, as the calibration procedure relies exclusively on the relative differences between countries, which are invariant to this linear transformation.

2.2 Analytical Notation

The following standardized notation is used throughout the analysis to ensure consistency and clarity.

- **Indices:**
 - Sectors are indexed by $i = 1, \dots, I$.
 - Countries or regions are indexed by $j = 1, \dots, J$.
- **Quantity-Price (QP) Variables:**
 - These variables are denoted by v and include key economic flows such as XS (Exports), CI (Intermediate Consumption), C (Final Consumption), LDC (Labor Demand), and KDC (Capital Demand).
 - For each QP variable, the model provides four components:
 - $q_{\{ij\}}^{v,0}$: pre-shock quantity
 - $q_{\{ij\}}^{v,1}$: post-shock quantity
 - $p_{\{ij\}}^{v,0}$: pre-shock price index (e.g., PP , PCI , WC , RC)
 - $p_{\{ij\}}^{v,1}$: post-shock price index (e.g., PP , PCI , WC , RC)
- **Income (Y) Variables:**
 - These variables are denoted by y and include income flows such as YDH (Household Disposable Income), YG (Government Income), YH (Household Income), YHK (Household Capital Income), YHL (Household Labor Income), and Y_ROW (Rest of World Income).
 - For each income variable, the model directly provides two components:
 - $Y_{\{j\}}^{y,0}$: pre-shock income value
 - $Y_{\{j\}}^{y,1}$: post-shock income value

This standardized notation provides the building blocks for calculating the initial economic changes for each variable resulting from the modeled shock.

3.0 Data Processing: Calculating Economic Changes (Deltas)

The analytical objective of this stage is to solve the initial data processing challenge: transforming the raw 'before' and 'after' model outputs into a set of 'delta' (Δ) values that represent the net change caused by the modeled shock. This calculation is performed differently for the two main categories of variables: Quantity-Price (QP) variables and Income (Y) variables.

3.1 Construction of Value Matrices for QP Variables

For each QP variable (XS, CI, C, LDC, and KDC), we calculate the change in value through a systematic, multi-step process following the sequencing-related technological shock (Scenario 1*).

1. **Compute Monetary Values:** We compute the monetary value before and after the shock for each sector-country pair (i,j) by multiplying the quantity by the corresponding price index.
2. **Calculate the Change in Value:** The change in value (ΔValue) for each sector-country pair is the difference between the post-shock and pre-shock values.
3. **Aggregate to the Country Level:** We then aggregate these changes to the country level by summing across all sectors (i).

This process yields a single country-level impact ($\Delta\text{Value}_{j}^{v}$), expressed in model million units, for each of the QP variables.

3.2 Derivation of Changes for Income (Y) Variables

We calculate the change for income variables (YDH, YG, YH, YHK, YHL, Y_ROW) more directly, as the GTAP model output provides the before- and after-shock values for each country without an explicit quantity-price decomposition.

We calculate the change in each income component y for each country j as a simple difference:

$$\Delta Y_{j}^{y} = Y_{j}^{y,1} - Y_{j}^{y,0}$$

These resulting ΔY values are also in model million units. Having calculated the delta for each individual variable, the next step is to combine them into a single, comprehensive measure of economic impact.

4.0 Aggregation: Constructing a Unified Country-Level Impact Score

The preceding calculations yield a granular set of economic changes across numerous variables. To derive a meaningful, country-level metric, these disparate impacts must be consolidated. This aggregation is not merely an accounting exercise; it is analytically necessary to synthesize the model's complex general equilibrium effects into a single, coherent score for each country.

The single aggregate impact, $\Delta_{j}^{\text{model}}$, is constructed for each country j by summing all individual QP and Y contributions:

$$\Delta_{j}^{\text{model}} = \sum_{v \in \text{QP}} \Delta\text{Value}_{j}^{v} + \sum_{y \in \text{Y}} \Delta Y_{j}^{y}$$

Where the terms are defined as:

- $\Sigma_{\{v \in \text{QP}\}}$: The sum over all Quantity-Price variables (XS, CI, C, LDC, KDC).
- $\Sigma_{\{y \in \text{Y}\}}$: The sum over all Income variables (YDH, YG, YH, YHK, YHL, Y_ROW).

The resulting $\Delta_{\{j\}}^{\{\text{model}\}}$ is a dimensionless, model-consistent measure of the net economic effect. It preserves the general equilibrium interactions across sectors and between production, factor incomes, and final demand. While this score accurately reflects the *relative* effects between countries, it must be calibrated to an external benchmark to determine its *absolute* value in real-world monetary terms.

5.0 Calibration: Anchoring Model Results to Real-World Economics

Calibration is the critical step that resolves the core analytical challenge. The GTAP shock represents a technological and behavioural perturbation (e.g., changes in total factor productivity and elasticities), not a direct monetary investment. Therefore, this calibration is essential to link the abstract, dimensionless model results ($\Delta_{\{j\}}^{\{\text{model}\}}$) to a tangible investment amount and its empirically observed economic return, thereby grounding the simulation in real-world economics.

5.1 The External Benchmark: The Morocco Cost-Benefit Analysis

The external anchor point for this calibration is a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) conducted for a genomic sequencing program in Morocco. This independent study provides the empirical data needed to scale the model's outputs.

The key data points from the external CBA are:

- **Investment Cost (I):** \$20,000,000 USD
- **Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) for Morocco:** 3.29
- **Implied Total Economic Benefit for Morocco ($B_{\text{target},\text{MAR}}$):** \$65,800,000 USD (calculated as $3.29 \times \$20,000,000$)

5.2 Deriving and Applying the Calibration Factor (k)

The core logic of the calibration is to use Morocco as an anchor to determine a conversion factor (k) that translates the model's abstract units into U.S. dollars. This approach preserves the proportional, cross-country impact pattern generated by the GTAP model while scaling the absolute magnitude to match the empirical benchmark.

We derive the calibration factor k by linking the model's output for Morocco ($\Delta_{\{\text{MAR}\}}^{\{\text{model}\}}$) to the target benefit from the external CBA:

$$k \times \Delta_{\{\text{MAR}\}}^{\{\text{model}\}} = B_{\text{target},\text{MAR}}$$

Solving for k gives the calibration factor:

$$k = B_{\text{target},\text{MAR}} / \Delta_{\{\text{MAR}\}}^{\{\text{model}\}}$$

This single factor k , expressed in USD per model unit, is then applied uniformly to all countries in the analysis, preparing for the final calculation of meaningful economic outputs.

6.0 Final Outputs: Calculating Calibrated Benefits and BCRs

This section represents the culmination of the entire analytical workflow. By applying the universally derived calibration factor, we transform the abstract model deltas into the final, interpretable economic indicators that are the primary goal of the analysis: absolute economic benefits and Benefit-Cost Ratios.

6.1 Calculating Calibrated Country-Level Benefits

We use the universal calibration factor k to convert each country's aggregate model delta ($\Delta_{\{j\}}^{\{\text{model}\}}$) into a calibrated economic benefit expressed in U.S. dollars. The calculation is a straightforward application of the factor:

$$\text{Benefit}_{\{j\}} = k \times \Delta_{\{j\}}^{\{\text{model}\}}$$

6.2 Calculating Calibrated Country-Level Benefit-Cost Ratios (BCRs)

The final step is to calculate the calibrated Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) for each country j . We calculate the calibrated BCR by dividing the calibrated benefit by the standardized investment cost ($I = \$20,000,000$ USD).

The primary formula is:

$$\text{BCR}_{\{j\}}^{\{\text{calibrated}\}} = \text{Benefit}_{\{j\}} / I$$

By substituting the formulas from the previous steps, we can express the BCR in terms of the underlying model delta:

$$\text{BCR}_{\{j\}}^{\{\text{calibrated}\}} = (k \times \Delta_{\{j\}}^{\{\text{model}\}}) / I$$

Finally, substituting the definition of k yields the most intuitive and powerful expression of the relationship. This form highlights how each country's calibrated BCR is directly proportional to its GTAP-derived effect relative to Morocco's, anchored by Morocco's externally validated BCR.

$$\text{BCR}_{\{j\}}^{\{\text{calibrated}\}} = (\Delta_{\{j\}}^{\{\text{model}\}} / \Delta_{\{\text{MAR}\}}^{\{\text{model}\}}) \times \text{BCR}_{\{\text{MAR}\}}^{\{\text{external}\}}$$

This final expression elegantly demonstrates the methodology's core logic: it takes a unitless, relative impact ratio from the CGE model ($\Delta_{\{j\}}^{\{\text{model}\}} /$

$\Delta_{\text{MAR}}^{\text{model}}$) and scales it by a real-world, empirically validated return on investment ($\text{BCR}_{\text{MAR}}^{\text{external}}$) to produce a set of policy-relevant, comparable BCRs for all other countries.

This methodology demonstrates three core strengths. First, it preserves the global structure and cross-country ranking of economic impacts as determined by the GTAP general equilibrium model. Second, it anchors the absolute magnitude of benefits to a real-world, external economic assessment. And third, it produces final BCRs that are directly and consistently interpretable as the economic return on a standard \$20 million investment in sequencing technology.

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